

Different Types and Aspects of Magic Squares of Order 15

The whole work as pdf files is available at author's sites:
<https://numbers-magic.com/?p=16911>

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Abstract

*This work summarizes author's previous works on magic squares of order 15. It brings different types of magic square such as **block-wise, single-digit bordered, double-digit bordered, cornered, designs, styles, etc.** In terms of aspects, we have considered the idea of **Pythagorean triples, upside-down, mirror-looking, water reflection, perfect square sum entries, Latin square distributions, algebraic magic squares, etc.***

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Contents

1	Introduction	3
2	Different Types of Magic Squares of Order 15	4
2.1	Block-Wise Magic Squares	4
2.2	Single-Digit Bordered Magic Squares	7
2.3	Cornered Magic Squares	9
2.4	Double-Digits Bordered Magic Squares	10
2.5	Double-Digits Embedded Magic Squares	13
2.6	Triple-Digit Bordered Magic Squares	15
3	Different Aspects of Magic Squares of Order 15	17
3.1	Latin Square Distributions	17
3.2	Perfect Square Entries Sum	20
3.2.1	Uniformity Property	20
3.2.2	Pythagorean Triple	22
3.2.3	Minimum Perfect Square Sum of Entries	24
3.3	Upside-Down, Mirror Looking and Water Reflection	25
3.3.1	Upside-Down and Mirror Looking Magic Squares	26
3.3.2	Water Reflection and Magic Squares	37
3.4	Self-Made Algebraic Magic Squares of Order 15	50
3.4.1	Equal Sum Magic Squares of Order 5	50
3.4.2	Equal Sum Magic Squares of Order 3	53
3.4.3	Double-Digit Bordered	56
4	Author's Contribution to Magic Squares and Recreation of Numbers	59

1 Introduction

In the previous works [19, 20, 21, 22, 23, 24, 25], the author worked with **block-wise** constructions of magic squares. The work is from the orders 8 to 45. In each case, all the possibilities are considered. These possibilities are based on divisions of magic squares. The magic sums of order n of consecutive numbers from 1 to n^2 is given by

$$S_{n \times n} := \frac{n \times (1 + n^2)}{2}, n \geq 3. \quad (1)$$

This formula is applied to all order magic squares. Based on this formula we shall bring **blocks** for the **block-wise** magic squares. That is, whenever is possible, we shall try to bring blocks of equal sum magic squares. In some cases, they are **magic, semi-magic, pandiagonal**, etc. When the question come to **bimagic** squares, in some cases, we have **semi-bimagic** squares.

On the other hand the idea of **bordered** magic squares is well explained in the work by H.White [4, 5]. Few results in this direction can be seen in author's work [26, 27, 28, 29, 30, 31]. In some case, the magic rectangles are also used to write it in different styles. Most of the author's work on magic squares is summarized below in details according to topic:

1. *Digital Fonts: Upside-down and Mirror Looking.*
2. *Two Digits Universal Magic Squares.*
3. *Different Digits Magic Squares.*
4. *Pythagorean Triples Magic Squares.*
5. *Block-Wise Magic Squares.*
6. *Selfie and Palindromic Type Magic Squares.*
7. *Block Bordered Magic Squares.*
8. *Block-Wise Bordered Magic Squares.*
9. *Magic Crosses, Letters and Numbers.*
10. *Cornered Magic Squares.*
11. *Single-Digit Bordered Magic Squares.*
12. *Double-Digit Bordered Magic Squares.*
13. *Multiple-Digit Bordered Magic Squares.*
14. *Striped Magic Squares.*
15. *Upside-down and Mirror Looking.*
16. *Water reflection Magic Squares.*

17. *Algebraic Maic Squares.*

The aim of this work is to write magic squares of order 16 in different ways and styles using the aspects of **blocks**, **bordered**, **block-bordered** and **magic rectangles**, **corner-type**, **single-digit**, **double-digit**, etc.

More details on these works on **magic squares** can be seen in author's web-sites:

(i) <https://numbers-magic.com/?p=668>

(ii) <https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/2019/06/27/publications-magic-squares/>

2 Different Types of Magic Squares of Order 15

According to Equation (1), the magic sum of order 15 is given by

$$S_{15 \times 15} := \frac{15 \times (1 + 15^2)}{2} = 1695.$$

We can write, $15 := 3 \times 5$. This gives the possibilities of blocks of orders 3 and 5. Let's see the divisions of magic square sum 1695 by 5 and 3:

- (i) $\frac{1595}{5} = 339 \implies$ equal or unequal sum blocks of order 3;
- (ii) $\frac{29679}{3} = 565 \implies$ equal sum blocks of order 5.

2.1 Block-Wise Magic Squares

Example 2.1.

	pan	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695
1695	186	65	88	187	74	78	188	75	76	189	64	86	190	62	87	1695
1695	80	193	66	89	183	67	90	181	68	79	191	69	77	192	70	1695
1695	73	81	185	63	82	194	61	83	195	71	84	184	72	85	182	1695
1695	36	200	103	37	209	93	38	210	91	39	199	101	40	197	102	1695
1695	95	43	201	104	33	202	105	31	203	94	41	204	92	42	205	1695
1695	208	96	35	198	97	44	196	98	45	206	99	34	207	100	32	1695
1695	6	215	118	7	224	108	8	225	106	9	214	116	10	212	117	1695
1695	110	13	216	119	3	217	120	1	218	109	11	219	107	12	220	1695
1695	223	111	5	213	112	14	211	113	15	221	114	4	222	115	2	1695
1695	156	50	133	157	59	123	158	60	121	159	49	131	160	47	132	1695
1695	125	163	51	134	153	52	135	151	53	124	161	54	122	162	55	1695
1695	58	126	155	48	127	164	46	128	165	56	129	154	57	130	152	1695
1695	171	20	148	172	29	138	173	30	136	174	19	146	175	17	147	1695
1695	140	178	21	149	168	22	150	166	23	139	176	24	137	177	25	1695
	28	141	170	18	142	179	16	143	180	26	144	169	27	145	167	1695
	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695

Example 2.2.

	pan	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695
1695	1	87	111	178	188	3	86	110	179	187	2	85	109	180	189	1695
1695	171	193	8	76	117	170	194	7	78	116	169	195	9	77	115	1695
1695	83	106	177	186	13	82	108	176	185	14	84	107	175	184	15	1695
1695	192	6	88	113	166	191	5	89	112	168	190	4	90	114	167	1695
1695	118	173	181	12	81	119	172	183	11	80	120	174	182	10	79	1695
1695	31	72	96	163	203	33	71	95	164	202	32	70	94	165	204	1695
1695	156	208	38	61	102	155	209	37	63	101	154	210	39	62	100	1695
1695	68	91	162	201	43	67	93	161	200	44	69	92	160	199	45	1695
1695	207	36	73	98	151	206	35	74	97	153	205	34	75	99	152	1695
1695	103	158	196	42	66	104	157	198	41	65	105	159	197	40	64	1695
1695	16	57	126	148	218	18	56	125	149	217	17	55	124	150	219	1695
1695	141	223	23	46	132	140	224	22	48	131	139	225	24	47	130	1695
1695	53	121	147	216	28	52	123	146	215	29	54	122	145	214	30	1695
1695	222	21	58	128	136	221	20	59	127	138	220	19	60	129	137	1695
	133	143	211	27	51	134	142	213	26	50	135	144	212	25	49	1695
	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695

2.2 Single-Digit Bordered Magic Squares

Example 2.3.

mgc	15x15 https://numbers-magic.com/ https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/ ©IJT													1695	
210	199	201	203	205	207	209	211	11	9	7	5	3	1	14	1695
2	184	175	177	179	181	183	185	37	35	33	31	29	40	224	1695
4	30	64	72	70	68	66	165	166	168	170	172	62	196	222	1695
6	32	173	80	152	150	148	147	84	86	88	82	53	194	220	1695
8	34	171	73	130	126	128	93	92	90	132	153	55	192	218	1695
10	36	169	75	89	122	125	105	107	106	137	151	57	190	216	1695
12	38	167	77	91	102	112	117	110	124	135	149	59	188	214	1695
13	39	63	145	131	103	111	113	115	123	95	81	163	187	213	1695
208	182	65	143	129	118	116	109	114	108	97	83	161	44	18	1695
206	180	67	141	127	120	101	121	119	104	99	85	159	46	20	1695
204	178	69	139	94	100	98	133	134	136	96	87	157	48	22	1695
202	176	71	144	74	76	78	79	142	140	138	146	155	50	24	1695
200	174	164	154	156	158	160	61	60	58	56	54	162	52	26	1695
198	186	51	49	47	45	43	41	189	191	193	195	197	42	28	1695
212	27	25	23	21	19	17	15	215	217	219	221	223	225	16	1695
1695	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695

Example 2.4.

mgc	15x15 https://numbers-magic.com/ https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/ ©IJT										1695				
97	100	80	82	81	222	225	205	207	206	47	50	30	32	31	1695
77	87	92	85	99	202	212	217	210	224	27	37	42	35	49	1695
78	86	88	90	98	203	211	213	215	223	28	36	38	40	48	1695
93	91	84	89	83	218	216	209	214	208	43	41	34	39	33	1695
95	76	96	94	79	220	201	221	219	204	45	26	46	44	29	1695
72	75	55	57	56	122	125	105	107	106	172	175	155	157	156	1695
52	62	67	60	74	102	112	117	110	124	152	162	167	160	174	1695
53	61	63	65	73	103	111	113	115	123	153	161	163	165	173	1695
68	66	59	64	58	118	116	109	114	108	168	166	159	164	158	1695
70	51	71	69	54	120	101	121	119	104	170	151	171	169	154	1695
197	200	180	182	181	22	25	5	7	6	147	150	130	132	131	1695
177	187	192	185	199	2	12	17	10	24	127	137	142	135	149	1695
178	186	188	190	198	3	11	13	15	23	128	136	138	140	148	1695
193	191	184	189	183	18	16	9	14	8	143	141	134	139	133	1695
195	176	196	194	179	20	1	21	19	4	145	126	146	144	129	1695
1695	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695

2.3 Cornered Magic Squares

Example 2.5.

mgc	15x15 https://numbers-magic.com/ https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/ ©IJT														1695
110	117	112	125	101	127	99	144	82	67	159	52	174	9	217	1695
115	113	111	124	102	133	93	142	84	64	162	41	185	3	223	1695
114	109	116	104	122	94	132	79	147	167	59	40	186	8	218	1695
108	106	123	107	121	89	137	78	148	168	58	184	42	205	21	1695
118	120	103	105	119	92	134	140	86	63	163	50	176	7	219	1695
90	91	131	128	129	126	96	138	88	62	164	191	35	201	25	1695
136	135	95	98	97	130	100	146	80	171	55	195	31	213	13	1695
149	153	87	83	81	151	85	76	152	172	54	190	36	206	20	1695
77	73	139	143	145	75	141	74	150	71	155	45	181	1	225	1695
70	60	69	170	165	72	169	66	68	173	161	51	175	203	23	1695
156	166	157	56	61	154	57	160	158	65	53	196	30	6	220	1695
180	34	182	183	179	32	187	33	177	38	178	37	29	215	11	1695
46	192	44	43	47	194	39	193	49	188	48	197	189	10	216	1695
224	221	211	26	17	212	19	24	214	222	22	18	27	210	28	1695
2	5	15	200	209	14	207	202	12	4	204	208	199	198	16	1695
1695	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695

2.4 Double-Digits Bordered Magic Squares

Example 2.6.

mgc	15x15 https://numbers-magic.com/ https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/ ©IJT														1695
205	212	49	46	200	196	188	36	32	7	50	213	35	34	192	1695
21	14	177	180	26	30	38	190	194	219	176	13	191	44	182	1695
201	25	62	85	168	66	80	162	159	163	72	69	157	220	6	1695
216	10	164	141	58	160	146	64	67	63	154	153	73	45	181	1695
11	215	152	74	121	98	108	101	137	120	106	144	82	48	178	1695
41	185	169	57	105	128	118	125	89	93	133	70	156	23	203	1695
193	33	79	147	102	124	116	109	114	90	136	170	56	175	51	1695
197	29	59	167	127	99	111	113	115	130	96	150	76	208	18	1695
17	209	68	158	95	131	112	117	110	132	94	53	173	222	4	1695
3	223	143	83	107	119	91	122	129	100	123	60	166	1	225	1695
8	218	87	139	134	92	135	104	97	126	103	148	78	211	15	1695
195	31	172	54	171	77	86	75	155	81	65	165	142	28	198	1695
19	207	88	138	55	149	140	151	71	145	161	61	84	210	16	1695
189	37	52	199	39	20	214	43	186	42	5	204	24	224	217	1695
179	47	174	27	187	206	12	183	40	184	221	22	202	2	9	1695
1695	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695

Example 2.7.

mgc	15x15 https://numbers-magic.com/ https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/ ©IJT														1695
208	193	206	29	209	1	3	181	201	38	8	205	195	16	2	1695
18	33	20	197	17	225	223	45	25	188	218	21	31	210	224	1695
22	204	83	73	82	150	81	151	56	165	87	158	157	186	40	1695
213	13	143	153	144	76	145	75	170	61	139	68	69	35	191	1695
32	194	66	160	97	131	132	137	93	103	98	77	149	212	14	1695
182	44	138	88	129	95	94	89	133	123	128	78	148	216	10	1695
185	41	57	169	124	102	114	115	110	136	90	168	58	220	6	1695
15	211	166	60	107	119	109	113	117	99	127	72	154	26	200	1695
174	52	155	71	108	118	116	111	112	104	122	140	86	46	180	1695
12	214	63	163	100	105	134	130	106	125	91	85	141	28	198	1695
183	43	146	80	126	121	92	96	120	101	135	171	55	27	199	1695
47	179	64	65	147	156	173	67	54	164	59	142	152	196	30	1695
178	48	162	161	79	70	53	159	172	62	167	84	74	51	175	1695
176	190	42	23	219	19	189	187	5	4	34	11	177	202	217	1695
50	36	184	203	7	207	37	39	221	222	192	215	49	24	9	1695
1695	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695

Example 2.8.

mgc	15x15 https://numbers-magic.com/ https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/ ©IJT												1695		
20	8	209	211	22	186	42	225	26	47	217	222	34	194	32	1695
206	218	17	15	204	40	184	1	200	179	9	4	192	28	198	1695
175	51	85	84	81	172	74	61	144	168	148	154	72	183	43	1695
193	33	141	142	145	54	152	165	82	58	78	163	63	215	11	1695
180	46	88	138	128	136	106	104	91	132	94	87	139	212	14	1695
35	191	77	149	98	90	120	122	135	126	100	83	143	219	7	1695
18	208	57	169	102	124	114	109	116	89	137	66	160	52	174	1695
19	207	76	150	96	130	115	113	111	121	105	75	151	24	202	1695
6	220	60	166	107	119	110	117	112	97	129	159	67	49	177	1695
224	2	173	53	127	99	125	134	108	103	95	171	55	13	213	1695
25	201	155	71	133	93	101	92	118	123	131	59	167	21	205	1695
176	50	170	56	69	62	162	140	153	68	70	146	147	36	190	1695
178	48	161	65	157	164	64	86	73	158	156	80	79	223	3	1695
37	189	195	16	10	30	182	188	181	5	185	214	197	27	39	1695
203	23	31	210	216	196	44	38	45	221	41	12	29	199	187	1695
1695	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695

2.5 Double-Digits Embedded Magic Squares

Example 2.9.

mgc	15x15 https://numbers-magic.com/ https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/ ©IJT														1695
205	212	49	46	200	196	188	36	32	7	50	213	35	34	192	1695
21	14	177	180	26	30	38	190	194	219	176	13	191	44	182	1695
201	25	64	72	70	68	66	165	166	168	170	172	62	220	6	1695
216	10	173	80	152	150	148	147	84	86	88	82	53	45	181	1695
11	215	171	73	130	126	128	93	92	90	132	153	55	48	178	1695
41	185	169	75	89	122	125	105	107	106	137	151	57	23	203	1695
193	33	167	77	91	102	112	117	110	124	135	149	59	175	51	1695
197	29	63	145	131	103	111	113	115	123	95	81	163	208	18	1695
17	209	65	143	129	118	116	109	114	108	97	83	161	222	4	1695
3	223	67	141	127	120	101	121	119	104	99	85	159	1	225	1695
8	218	69	139	94	100	98	133	134	136	96	87	157	211	15	1695
195	31	71	144	74	76	78	79	142	140	138	146	155	28	198	1695
19	207	164	154	156	158	160	61	60	58	56	54	162	210	16	1695
189	37	52	199	39	20	214	43	186	42	5	204	24	224	217	1695
179	47	174	27	187	206	12	183	40	184	221	22	202	2	9	1695
1695	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695

Example 2.10.

mgc	15x15 https://numbers-magic.com/ https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/ ©IJT												1695		
20	8	209	211	22	186	42	225	26	47	217	222	34	194	32	1695
206	218	17	15	204	40	184	1	200	179	9	4	192	28	198	1695
175	51	110	115	114	119	107	126	100	79	147	71	155	183	43	1695
193	33	117	113	109	120	106	133	93	88	138	162	64	215	11	1695
180	46	112	111	116	102	124	130	96	84	142	65	161	212	14	1695
35	191	108	104	105	123	125	127	99	86	140	172	54	219	7	1695
18	208	118	122	121	101	103	91	135	149	77	67	159	52	174	1695
19	207	128	92	129	132	90	89	131	146	80	63	163	24	202	1695
6	220	98	134	97	94	136	95	137	85	141	167	59	49	177	1695
224	2	150	151	87	81	82	83	153	152	78	168	58	13	213	1695
25	201	76	75	139	145	144	143	73	148	74	72	154	21	205	1695
176	50	164	56	158	55	53	157	61	160	57	166	156	36	190	1695
178	48	62	170	68	171	173	69	165	66	169	70	60	223	3	1695
37	189	195	16	10	30	182	188	181	5	185	214	197	27	39	1695
203	23	31	210	216	196	44	38	45	221	41	12	29	199	187	1695
1695	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695

2.6 Triple-Digit Bordered Magic Squares

Example 2.11.

mgc	15x15 https://numbers-magic.com/ https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/ ©IJT												1695		
195	190	197	159	154	161	24	19	26	15	10	17	177	172	179	1695
196	194	192	160	158	156	25	23	21	16	14	12	178	176	174	1695
191	198	193	155	162	157	20	27	22	11	18	13	173	180	175	1695
60	55	62	141	136	143	78	73	80	123	118	125	168	163	170	1695
61	59	57	142	140	138	79	77	75	124	122	120	169	167	165	1695
56	63	58	137	144	139	74	81	76	119	126	121	164	171	166	1695
42	37	44	96	91	98	114	109	116	132	127	134	186	181	188	1695
43	41	39	97	95	93	115	113	111	133	131	129	187	185	183	1695
38	45	40	92	99	94	110	117	112	128	135	130	182	189	184	1695
222	217	224	105	100	107	150	145	152	87	82	89	6	1	8	1695
223	221	219	106	104	102	151	149	147	88	86	84	7	5	3	1695
218	225	220	101	108	103	146	153	148	83	90	85	2	9	4	1695
51	46	53	69	64	71	204	199	206	213	208	215	33	28	35	1695
52	50	48	70	68	66	205	203	201	214	212	210	34	32	30	1695
47	54	49	65	72	67	200	207	202	209	216	211	29	36	31	1695
1695	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695

Example 2.12.

mgc	15x15 https://numbers-magic.com/ https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/ ©IJT												1695		
195	190	197	159	154	161	24	19	26	15	10	17	177	172	179	1695
196	194	192	160	158	156	25	23	21	16	14	12	178	176	174	1695
191	198	193	155	162	157	20	27	22	11	18	13	173	180	175	1695
60	55	62	80	152	150	148	147	84	86	88	82	168	163	170	1695
61	59	57	73	130	126	128	93	92	90	132	153	169	167	165	1695
56	63	58	75	89	122	125	105	107	106	137	151	164	171	166	1695
42	37	44	77	91	102	112	117	110	124	135	149	186	181	188	1695
43	41	39	145	131	103	111	113	115	123	95	81	187	185	183	1695
38	45	40	143	129	118	116	109	114	108	97	83	182	189	184	1695
222	217	224	141	127	120	101	121	119	104	99	85	6	1	8	1695
223	221	219	139	94	100	98	133	134	136	96	87	7	5	3	1695
218	225	220	144	74	76	78	79	142	140	138	146	2	9	4	1695
51	46	53	69	64	71	204	199	206	213	208	215	33	28	35	1695
52	50	48	70	68	66	205	203	201	214	212	210	34	32	30	1695
47	54	49	65	72	67	200	207	202	209	216	211	29	36	31	1695
1695	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695	1695

3 Different Aspects of Magic Squares of Order 15

Below are few examples of magic square of order 14 representing different aspects. Initially we shall present the idea of Latin square distributions.

3.1 Latin Square Distributions

Example 3.1. A pair of Latin square decomposition of magic square of order 15 given in Example 3.35 is as follows:

(A)																120
1	6	7	12	13	3	4	9	10	15	2	5	8	11	14		120
12	13	1	6	7	10	15	3	4	9	11	14	2	5	8		120
6	7	12	13	1	4	9	10	15	3	5	8	11	14	2		120
13	1	6	7	12	15	3	4	9	10	14	2	5	8	11		120
7	12	13	1	6	9	10	15	3	4	8	11	14	2	5		120
3	4	9	10	15	2	5	8	11	14	1	6	7	12	13		120
10	15	3	4	9	11	14	2	5	8	12	13	1	6	7		120
4	9	10	15	3	5	8	11	14	2	6	7	12	13	1		120
15	3	4	9	10	14	2	5	8	11	13	1	6	7	12		120
9	10	15	3	4	8	11	14	2	5	7	12	13	1	6		120
2	5	8	11	14	1	6	7	12	13	3	4	9	10	15		120
11	14	2	5	8	12	13	1	6	7	10	15	3	4	9		120
5	8	11	14	2	6	7	12	13	1	4	9	10	15	3		120
14	2	5	8	11	13	1	6	7	12	15	3	4	9	10		120
8	11	14	2	5	7	12	13	1	6	9	10	15	3	4		120
120	120	120	120	120	120	120	120	120	120	120	120	120	120	120	120	120

(B)															120
2	11	5	14	8	3	10	4	15	9	1	12	6	13	7	120
5	14	8	2	11	4	15	9	3	10	6	13	7	1	12	120
8	2	11	5	14	9	3	10	4	15	7	1	12	6	13	120
11	5	14	8	2	10	4	15	9	3	12	6	13	7	1	120
14	8	2	11	5	15	9	3	10	4	13	7	1	12	6	120
1	12	6	13	7	2	11	5	14	8	3	10	4	15	9	120
6	13	7	1	12	5	14	8	2	11	4	15	9	3	10	120
7	1	12	6	13	8	2	11	5	14	9	3	10	4	15	120
12	6	13	7	1	11	5	14	8	2	10	4	15	9	3	120
13	7	1	12	6	14	8	2	11	5	15	9	3	10	4	120
3	10	4	15	9	1	12	6	13	7	2	11	5	14	8	120
4	15	9	3	10	6	13	7	1	12	5	14	8	2	11	120
9	3	10	4	15	7	1	12	6	13	8	2	11	5	14	120
10	4	15	9	3	12	6	13	7	1	11	5	14	8	2	120
15	9	3	10	4	13	7	1	12	6	14	8	2	11	5	120
120	120	120	120	120	120	120	120	120	120	120	120	120	120	120	120

By application of the formula $15 \times (A - 1) + B$, we get a magic square given in Example 2.1.

Grid 1. Let's write the above Latin squares in terms of a Grid representing the numbers in alphabets:

a	f	g	l	m	c	d	i	j	p	b	e	h	k	n
l	m	a	f	g	j	p	c	d	i	k	n	b	e	h
f	g	l	m	a	d	i	j	p	c	e	h	k	n	b
m	a	f	g	l	p	c	d	i	j	n	b	e	h	k
g	l	m	a	f	i	j	p	c	d	h	k	n	b	e
c	d	i	j	p	b	e	h	k	n	a	f	g	l	m
j	p	c	d	i	k	n	b	e	h	l	m	a	f	g
d	i	j	p	c	e	h	k	n	b	f	g	l	m	a
p	c	d	i	j	n	b	e	h	k	m	a	f	g	l
i	j	p	c	d	h	k	n	b	e	g	l	m	a	f
b	e	h	k	n	a	f	g	l	m	c	d	i	j	p
k	n	b	e	h	l	m	a	f	g	j	p	c	d	i
e	h	k	n	b	f	g	l	m	a	d	i	j	p	c
n	b	e	h	k	m	a	f	g	l	p	c	d	i	j
h	k	n	b	e	g	l	m	a	f	i	j	p	c	d
							A							

b	k	e	n	h	c	j	d	p	i	a	l	f	m	g
e	n	h	b	k	d	p	i	c	j	f	m	g	a	l
h	b	k	e	n	i	c	j	d	p	g	a	l	f	m
k	e	n	h	b	j	d	p	i	c	l	f	m	g	a
n	h	b	k	e	p	i	c	j	d	m	g	a	l	f
a	l	f	m	g	b	k	e	n	h	c	j	d	p	i
f	m	g	a	l	e	n	h	b	k	d	p	i	c	j
g	a	l	f	m	h	b	k	e	n	i	c	j	d	p
l	f	m	g	a	k	e	n	h	b	j	d	p	i	c
m	g	a	l	f	n	h	b	k	e	p	i	c	j	d
c	j	d	p	i	a	l	f	m	g	b	k	e	n	h
d	p	i	c	j	f	m	g	a	l	e	n	h	b	k
i	c	j	d	p	g	a	l	f	m	h	b	k	e	n
j	d	p	i	c	l	f	m	g	a	k	e	n	h	b
p	i	c	j	d	m	g	a	l	f	n	h	b	k	e
							A							

It is the general procedure to write magic squares of order 15 by applying the condition $15 \times (A - 1) + B$ and choosing properly the value of letters.

3.2 Perfect Square Entries Sum

Below are five different magic squares of order 15 resulting in **uniformity**, **Pythagorean triples** and **minimum perfect square entries sum** properties.

3.2.1 Uniformity Property

Example 3.2. For the consecutive odd numbers entries $\{1, 3, 5, \dots, 447, 449\}$, a *pandiagonal* magic square of order 15 is given by

	pan	3375														
3375	1	173	221	355	375	5	171	219	357	373	3	169	217	359	377	3375
3375	341	385	15	151	233	339	387	13	155	231	337	389	17	153	229	3375
3375	165	211	353	371	25	163	215	351	369	27	167	213	349	367	29	3375
3375	383	11	175	225	331	381	9	177	223	335	379	7	179	227	333	3375
3375	235	345	361	23	161	237	343	365	21	159	239	347	363	19	157	3375
3375	61	143	191	325	405	65	141	189	327	403	63	139	187	329	407	3375
3375	311	415	75	121	203	309	417	73	125	201	307	419	77	123	199	3375
3375	135	181	323	401	85	133	185	321	399	87	137	183	319	397	89	3375
3375	413	71	145	195	301	411	69	147	193	305	409	67	149	197	303	3375
3375	205	315	391	83	131	207	313	395	81	129	209	317	393	79	127	3375
3375	31	113	251	295	435	35	111	249	297	433	33	109	247	299	437	3375
3375	281	445	45	91	263	279	447	43	95	261	277	449	47	93	259	3375
3375	105	241	293	431	55	103	245	291	429	57	107	243	289	427	59	3375
3375	443	41	115	255	271	441	39	117	253	275	439	37	119	257	273	3375
	265	285	421	53	101	267	283	425	51	99	269	287	423	49	97	3375
	3375	3375	3375	3375	3375	3375	3375	3375	3375	3375	3375	3375	3375	3375	3375	3375

Example 3.3. For the consecutive natural numbers entries $\{113, 114, 115, \dots, 336, 337\}$, a *pandiagonal* magic square of order 15 is given by

	pan	3375	3375	3375	3375	3375	3375	3375	3375	3375	3375	3375	3375	3375	3375	3375
3375	113	199	223	290	300	115	198	222	291	299	114	197	221	292	301	3375
3375	283	305	120	188	229	282	306	119	190	228	281	307	121	189	227	3375
3375	195	218	289	298	125	194	220	288	297	126	196	219	287	296	127	3375
3375	304	118	200	225	278	303	117	201	224	280	302	116	202	226	279	3375
3375	230	285	293	124	193	231	284	295	123	192	232	286	294	122	191	3375
3375	143	184	208	275	315	145	183	207	276	314	144	182	206	277	316	3375
3375	268	320	150	173	214	267	321	149	175	213	266	322	151	174	212	3375
3375	180	203	274	313	155	179	205	273	312	156	181	204	272	311	157	3375
3375	319	148	185	210	263	318	147	186	209	265	317	146	187	211	264	3375
3375	215	270	308	154	178	216	269	310	153	177	217	271	309	152	176	3375
3375	128	169	238	260	330	130	168	237	261	329	129	167	236	262	331	3375
3375	253	335	135	158	244	252	336	134	160	243	251	337	136	159	242	3375
3375	165	233	259	328	140	164	235	258	327	141	166	234	257	326	142	3375
3375	334	133	170	240	248	333	132	171	239	250	332	131	172	241	249	3375
	245	255	323	139	163	246	254	325	138	162	247	256	324	137	161	3375
	3375	3375	3375	3375	3375	3375	3375	3375	3375	3375	3375	3375	3375	3375	3375	3375

In both the Examples 3.2 and 3.3, the magic sums are equal. The blocks of order 5 are **pandiagonal** magic squares with equal magic sums. See below the details:

$$S_{15 \times 15} := 3375; \quad T_{225} := 15 \times 3375 = 50625 = 225^2 = 15^4;$$

$$S_{5 \times 5} = 1125; \quad T_{25} := 5 \times 1125 = 5625 = 75^2.$$

The Examples 3.2 and 3.3 also satisfy the **uniformity property**, i.e., $\langle 15, 15^2, 15^3, 15^4 \rangle$.

3.2.2 Pythagorean Triple

Example 3.4. For the consecutive odd numbers entries $\{65, 67, \dots, 511, 513\}$, a *pandiagonal* magic square of order 15 is given by

	pan	4335	4335	4335	4335	4335	4335	4335	4335	4335	4335	4335	4335	4335	4335	4335
4335	435	193	239	437	211	219	439	213	215	441	191	235	443	187	237	4335
4335	223	449	195	241	429	197	243	425	199	221	445	201	217	447	203	4335
4335	209	225	433	189	227	451	185	229	453	205	231	431	207	233	427	4335
4335	135	463	269	137	481	249	139	483	245	141	461	265	143	457	267	4335
4335	253	149	465	271	129	467	273	125	469	251	145	471	247	147	473	4335
4335	479	255	133	459	257	151	455	259	153	475	261	131	477	263	127	4335
4335	75	493	299	77	511	279	79	513	275	81	491	295	83	487	297	4335
4335	283	89	495	301	69	497	303	65	499	281	85	501	277	87	503	4335
4335	509	285	73	489	287	91	485	289	93	505	291	71	507	293	67	4335
4335	375	163	329	377	181	309	379	183	305	381	161	325	383	157	327	4335
4335	313	389	165	331	369	167	333	365	169	311	385	171	307	387	173	4335
4335	179	315	373	159	317	391	155	319	393	175	321	371	177	323	367	4335
4335	405	103	359	407	121	339	409	123	335	411	101	355	413	97	357	4335
4335	343	419	105	361	399	107	363	395	109	341	415	111	337	417	113	4335
	119	345	403	99	347	421	95	349	423	115	351	401	117	353	397	4335
	4335	4335	4335	4335	4335	4335	4335	4335	4335	4335	4335	4335	4335	4335	4335	4335

Example 3.5. For the consecutive natural numbers entries $\{177, 178, \dots, 400, 401\}$, a *pandiagonal* magic square of order 15 is given by

	pan	4335	4335	4335	4335	4335	4335	4335	4335	4335	4335	4335	4335	4335	4335	4335
4335	362	241	264	363	250	254	364	251	252	365	240	262	366	238	263	4335
4335	256	369	242	265	359	243	266	357	244	255	367	245	253	368	246	4335
4335	249	257	361	239	258	370	237	259	371	247	260	360	248	261	358	4335
4335	212	376	279	213	385	269	214	386	267	215	375	277	216	373	278	4335
4335	271	219	377	280	209	378	281	207	379	270	217	380	268	218	381	4335
4335	384	272	211	374	273	220	372	274	221	382	275	210	383	276	208	4335
4335	182	391	294	183	400	284	184	401	282	185	390	292	186	388	293	4335
4335	286	189	392	295	179	393	296	177	394	285	187	395	283	188	396	4335
4335	399	287	181	389	288	190	387	289	191	397	290	180	398	291	178	4335
4335	332	226	309	333	235	299	334	236	297	335	225	307	336	223	308	4335
4335	301	339	227	310	329	228	311	327	229	300	337	230	298	338	231	4335
4335	234	302	331	224	303	340	222	304	341	232	305	330	233	306	328	4335
4335	347	196	324	348	205	314	349	206	312	350	195	322	351	193	323	4335
4335	316	354	197	325	344	198	326	342	199	315	352	200	313	353	201	4335
	204	317	346	194	318	355	192	319	356	202	320	345	203	321	343	4335
	4335	4335	4335	4335	4335	4335	4335	4335	4335	4335	4335	4335	4335	4335	4335	4335

In both the Examples 3.4 and 3.5, the magic sums are equal. The blocks of order 3 are **semi-magic** squares with equal **semi-magic** sums. See below the details:

$$S_{15 \times 15} := 4335; \quad T_{225} := 15 \times 4335 = 65025 = 255^2$$

$$Sm_{3 \times 3} := 867; \quad T_{225} := 3 \times 867 = 2601 = 51^2.$$

Both the Examples 3.4 and 3.5 are generated by **Pythagorean triple (32, 255, 257)**, i.e., $32^2 + 255^2 = 257^2$ with least possible sum of entries resulting in a **perfect square sum**.

3.2.3 Minimum Perfect Square Sum of Entries

Example 3.6. For the consecutive natural numbers entries $\{9, 10, 11, \dots, 232, 233\}$, a *pandiagonal* magic square of order 15 is given by

	pan	1815	1815	1815	1815	1815	1815	1815	1815	1815	1815	1815	1815	1815	1815	1815
1815	9	95	119	186	196	11	94	118	187	195	10	93	117	188	197	1815
1815	179	201	16	84	125	178	202	15	86	124	177	203	17	85	123	1815
1815	91	114	185	194	21	90	116	184	193	22	92	115	183	192	23	1815
1815	200	14	96	121	174	199	13	97	120	176	198	12	98	122	175	1815
1815	126	181	189	20	89	127	180	191	19	88	128	182	190	18	87	1815
1815	39	80	104	171	211	41	79	103	172	210	40	78	102	173	212	1815
1815	164	216	46	69	110	163	217	45	71	109	162	218	47	70	108	1815
1815	76	99	170	209	51	75	101	169	208	52	77	100	168	207	53	1815
1815	215	44	81	106	159	214	43	82	105	161	213	42	83	107	160	1815
1815	111	166	204	50	74	112	165	206	49	73	113	167	205	48	72	1815
1815	24	65	134	156	226	26	64	133	157	225	25	63	132	158	227	1815
1815	149	231	31	54	140	148	232	30	56	139	147	233	32	55	138	1815
1815	61	129	155	224	36	60	131	154	223	37	62	130	153	222	38	1815
1815	230	29	66	136	144	229	28	67	135	146	228	27	68	137	145	1815
	141	151	219	35	59	142	150	221	34	58	143	152	220	33	57	1815
	1815	1815	1815	1815	1815	1815	1815	1815	1815	1815	1815	1815	1815	1815	1815	1815

The entries sum is **minimum perfect square**. The blocks of order 5 are **pandiagonal** magic squares with equal magic sums. See below the details:

$$S_{15 \times 15} = 1815; \quad T_{729} := T_{225} := 15 \times 1815 = 27225 = 165^2$$

$$S_{5 \times 5} := 605; \quad T_{25} := 5 \times 605 = 3025 = 55^2.$$

3.3 Upside-Down, Mirror Looking and Water Reflection

Let's consider the following image:

Source: <https://www.mathsisfun.com/definitions/vertical-flip.html>

From the above image we understand that **horizontal flip** is same as **mirror looking image** and the **vertical flip** is same as **water reflection image**. The same terms are given in **paint brush of microsoft**. Let's see how it works on numbers.

Let's consider following 9 digits written in digital form:

0-1-2-3-4-5-6-7-8-9

- **180° Rotation**

6-8-1-9-5-4-2-1-0

In this case, the readable numbers are 0, 1, 2, 5, 6, 8 and 9 where the number 6 becomes 9 and 9 as 6. Thus the **survival numbers** after 180° rotation are 0, 1, 2, 5, 6, 8 and 9. Sometimes we call them as **upside-down** numbers.

- **Mirror Looking**

It is same as **horizontal flip** as describe above. In this case, we have

2-8-1-2-2-4-5-1-0

In this case, the readable numbers are 0, 1, 2, 5 and 8, where 2 becomes 5 and 5 as 2. Thus the **survival numbers** after **horizontal flip** are 0, 1, 2, 5 and 8. Sometimes we call them as **mirror-looking** numbers.

- **Water Reflection**

It is same as **vertical flip** as describe above. In this case, we have

0-1-5-3-4-2-2-1-8-2

In this case, the readable numbers are 0, 1, 2, 3, 5 and 8, where 2 becomes 5 and 5 as 2. Thus the **survival numbers** after **vertical flip** are 0, 1, 2, 3, 5 and 8. For the first time we call these numbers as **water reflection** or **water reflexive** numbers.

We observe that the numbers 0, 1, 2, 5 and 8 are in all the three situations, i.e., these are **upside-down**, **mirror-looking** and **water reflexive**. We call them as **universal numbers** provided they are written in **digital form**. There left only one number 3. It is only **water reflexive**. While the numbers 6 and 9 are only **upside-down**.

There is a lot of work by author on **upside-down** and **mirror-looking** numbers. This work is concentrated only towards magic squares having **water reflexive** numbers, i.e., 0, 1, 2, 3, 5 and 8. The numbers 0, 1, 2, 5 and 8 are already studied previously. This work brings magic squares of order 14 to 16 specially in number 3 along with 0, 1, 2, 5 and 8.

3.3.1 Upside-Down and Mirror Looking Magic Squares

Below are few examples of magic squares of order 15 having the property of **upside-down** and/or **mirror looking**

• **4-Digits Cell Entries**

Example 3.7. *Let's consider a magic square of order 15 with 4-digits (1,6,8,9) given by*

1618	6889	6966	9198	9681	1919	6188	8661	8899	9986	1816	6691	8168	8996	9869
9166	9698	1681	6818	6989	8861	9999	1986	6119	8688	8968	9896	1869	6616	8191
6881	6918	9189	9666	1698	6186	8619	8888	9961	1999	6669	8116	8991	9868	1896
9689	1666	6898	6981	9118	9988	1961	6199	8686	8819	9891	1868	6696	8169	8916
6998	9181	9618	1689	6866	8699	8886	9919	1988	6161	8196	8969	9816	1891	6668
1916	6191	8668	8896	9969	1818	6689	8166	8998	9881	1619	6888	6961	9199	9686
8868	9996	1969	6116	8691	8966	9898	1881	6618	8189	9161	9699	1686	6819	6988
6169	8616	8891	9968	1996	6681	8118	8989	9866	1898	6886	6919	9188	9661	1699
9991	1968	6196	8669	8816	9889	1866	6698	8181	8918	9688	1661	6899	6986	9119
8696	8869	9916	1991	6168	8198	8981	9818	1889	6666	6999	9186	9619	1688	6861
1819	6688	8161	8999	9886	1616	6891	6968	9196	9669	1918	6189	8666	8898	9981
8961	9899	1886	6619	8188	9168	9696	1669	6816	6991	8866	9998	1981	6118	8689
6686	8119	8988	9861	1899	6869	6916	9191	9668	1696	6181	8618	8889	9966	1998
9888	1861	6699	8186	8919	9691	1668	6896	6969	9116	9989	1966	6198	8681	8818
8199	8986	9819	1888	6661	6996	9169	9616	1691	6868	8698	8881	9918	1989	6166

The magic square of order 15 given above in Example 3.7 with 4-digits (1,6,8,9) is *upside-down semi-magic with semi-magic sum*, $S_{15 \times 15}(1,6,8,9) := 105545$. The blocks of order 5 are *pandiagonal magic squares*.

Example 3.8. Let's consider a magic square of order 15 with 4-digits (0,2,5,8) given by

0205	2558	2822	8085	8250	0808	2055	5220	5588	8852	0502	2280	5025	5882	8528
8022	8285	0250	2505	2858	5520	8888	0852	2008	5255	5825	8582	0528	2202	5080
2550	2805	8058	8222	0285	2052	5208	5555	8820	0888	2228	5002	5880	8525	0582
8258	0222	2585	2850	8005	8855	0820	2088	5252	5508	8580	0525	2282	5028	5802
2885	8050	8205	0258	2522	5288	5552	8808	0855	2020	5082	5828	8502	0580	2225
0802	2080	5225	5582	8828	0505	2258	5022	5885	8550	0208	2555	2820	8088	8252
5525	8882	0828	2002	5280	5822	8585	0550	2205	5058	8020	8288	0252	2508	2855
2028	5202	5580	8825	0882	2250	5005	5858	8522	0585	2552	2808	8055	8220	0288
8880	0825	2082	5228	5502	8558	0522	2285	5050	5805	8255	0220	2588	2852	8008
5282	5528	8802	0880	2025	5085	5850	8505	0558	2222	2888	8052	8208	0255	2520
0508	2255	5020	5888	8552	0202	2580	2825	8082	8228	0805	2058	5222	5585	8850
5820	8588	0552	2208	5055	8025	8282	0228	2502	2880	5522	8885	0850	2005	5258
2252	5008	5855	8520	0588	2528	2802	8080	8225	0282	2050	5205	5558	8822	0885
8555	0520	2288	5052	5808	8280	0225	2582	2828	8002	8858	0822	2085	5250	5505
5088	5852	8508	0555	2220	2882	8028	8202	0280	2525	5285	5550	8805	0858	2022

The magic square of order 15 given in Example 3.8 with 4-digits (0,2,5,8) is **universal** with magic sum, $S_{15 \times 15}(0, 2, 5, 8) := 66660$. Only in case of **mirror looking** situation it is **semi-magic**. The blocks of order 5 are **pandiagonal** magic squares with different magic sums.

• **6-Digits Cell Entries**

Example 3.9. *Let's consider a magic square of order 15 with 3-digits (1,6,9) given by*

111116	616919	666611	966996	991669	119119	166911	699166	911999	999699	116111	611966	669616	919991	996666
966611	991996	111669	616116	666919	911166	999999	119699	166119	699911	919616	996991	116666	611111	669966
616669	666116	966919	991611	111996	166699	699119	911911	999166	119999	611666	669111	919966	996616	116991
991919	111611	616996	666669	966116	999911	119166	166999	699699	911119	996966	116616	611991	669666	919111
666996	966669	991116	111919	616611	699999	911699	999119	119911	166166	669991	919666	996111	116966	611616
119111	166966	699616	911991	999666	116116	611919	669611	919996	996669	111119	616911	666166	966999	991699
911616	999991	119666	166111	699966	919611	996996	116669	611116	669919	966166	991999	111699	616119	666911
166666	699111	911966	999616	119991	611669	669116	919919	996611	116996	616699	666119	966911	991166	111999
999966	119616	166991	699666	911111	996919	116611	611996	669669	919116	991911	111166	616999	666699	966119
699991	911666	999111	119966	166616	669996	919669	996116	116919	611611	666999	966699	991119	111911	616166
116119	611911	669166	919999	996699	111111	616966	666616	966991	991666	119116	166919	699611	911996	999669
919166	996999	116699	611119	669911	966616	991991	111666	616111	666966	911611	999996	119669	166116	699919
611699	669119	919911	996166	116999	616666	666111	966966	991616	111991	166669	699116	911919	999611	119996
996911	116166	611999	669699	919119	991966	111616	616991	666666	966111	999919	119611	166996	699669	911116
669999	919699	996119	116911	611166	666991	966666	991111	111966	616616	699996	911669	999116	119919	166611

The magic square of order 15 given in Example 3.9 with 3-digits (1,6,9) is **upside-down semi-magic** with magic sum, $S_{14 \times 14}(1,6,9) := 9564555$. The blocks of order 5 are **pandiagonal** magic squares with different magic sums.

Example 3.10. Let's consider a magic square of order 15 with 4-digits (2,5,8) given by

222225	552828	555522	858885	882558	255255	288822	588288	822888	888588	225222	522858	558552	828882	885555
858522	882885	222558	552225	555828	822288	888888	255588	288255	588822	828552	885882	225555	522222	558858
552558	555225	858828	882522	222885	288588	588255	822822	888288	255888	522555	558222	828858	885552	225882
882828	222522	552885	555558	858225	888822	255288	288888	588588	822255	885858	225552	522882	558555	828222
555885	858558	882225	222828	552522	588888	822588	888255	255822	288288	558882	828555	885222	225858	522552
255222	288858	588552	822882	888555	225225	522828	558522	828885	885558	222255	552822	555288	858888	882588
822552	888882	255555	288222	588858	828522	885885	225558	522225	558828	858288	882888	222588	552255	555822
288555	588222	822858	888552	255882	522558	558225	828828	885522	225885	552588	555255	858822	882288	222888
888858	255552	288882	588555	822222	885828	225522	522885	558558	828225	882822	222288	552888	555588	858255
588882	822555	888222	255858	288552	558885	828558	885225	225828	522522	555888	858588	882255	222822	552288
225255	522822	558288	828888	885588	222222	552858	555552	858882	882555	255225	288828	588522	822885	888558
828288	885888	225588	522255	558822	858552	882882	222555	552222	555858	822522	888885	255558	288225	588828
522588	558255	828822	885288	225888	552555	555222	858858	882552	222882	288558	588225	822828	888522	255885
885822	225288	522888	558588	828255	882858	222552	552882	555555	858222	888828	255522	288885	588558	822225
558888	828588	885255	225822	522288	555882	858555	882222	222858	552552	588885	822558	888225	255828	288522

The magic square of order 15 given in Example 3.10 with 3-digits (2,5,8) is **universal** and **semi-magic** with different magic sums, i.e., the magic sums of original and **mirror looking** are the same, but in **upside-down** situation the sum is different, i.e., $SO_{15 \times 15}(2,5,8) := SM_{15 \times 15}(2,5,8) := 8936928$ and $SR_{15 \times 15}(2,5,8) := 8639631$.

• **8-Digits Cell: The Numbers 1 and 8 - Blocks of Order 5**

Example 3.11. *Let's consider a magic square of order 15 with 2-digits (1,8) given by*

1111118	18188181	18811811	81888818	88111888	11811181	11888118	81111188	81188881	88818111	11181111	18118188	18881818	81818811	88181881
81881811	88118818	11111888	18181118	18818181	81181188	88818881	11818111	11881181	81118118	81811818	88188811	11181881	18111111	18888188
18181888	18811118	81888181	88111811	11118818	11888111	81111181	81188118	88811188	11818881	18111881	18881111	81818188	88181818	11188811
88118181	11111811	18188818	18811888	81881118	88818118	11811188	11888881	81118111	81181181	88188188	11181818	18118811	18881881	81811111
18818818	81881888	88111118	11118181	18181811	81118881	81188111	88811181	11818118	11881188	18888811	81811881	88181111	11188188	18111818
11811111	11888188	81111818	81188811	88811881	11181118	18118181	18881811	81818818	88181888	11111181	18188118	18811188	81888881	88118111
81181818	88818811	11811881	11881111	81118188	81811811	88188818	11181888	18111118	18888181	81881188	88118881	11118111	18181181	18818118
11881881	81111111	81188188	88811818	11818811	18111888	18881118	81818181	88181811	11188818	18188111	18811181	81888118	88111188	11118881
88818188	11811818	11888811	81111881	81181111	88188181	11181811	18118818	18881888	81811118	88118118	11111188	18188881	18818111	81881181
81118811	81181881	88811111	11818188	11881818	18888818	81811888	88181118	11188181	18111811	18818881	81888111	88111181	11118118	18181188
11181181	18118118	18881188	81818881	88188111	11111111	18188188	18811818	81888811	88111881	11811118	11888181	81111811	81188818	88811888
81811188	88188881	11188111	18111181	18888118	81881818	88118811	11111881	18181111	18818188	81181811	88818818	11811888	11881118	81118181
18118111	18881181	81818118	88181188	11188881	18181881	18811111	81888188	88111818	11118811	11881888	81111118	81188181	88811811	11818818
88188118	11181188	18118881	18888111	81811181	88118188	11111818	18188811	18811881	81881111	88818181	11811811	11888818	81111888	81181118
18888881	81818111	88181181	11188118	18111188	18818811	81881881	88111111	11118188	18181818	81118818	81181888	88811118	11818181	11881811

The magic square of order 15 given in Example 3.11 with 2-digits (1,8) is **universal** and **semi-magic** with **semi-magic sum**: $S_{15 \times 15}(1,8) := 711111104$. Blocks of order 5 are **pandiagonal** magic squares with different magic sums.

• **8-Digits Cell: The Numbers 1 and 8 - Blocks of Order 3**

Example 3.12. *Let's consider a magic square of order 15 with 2-digits (1,8) with blocks of order 3:*

88111818	18111811	18188811	11811881	88188818	18811181	11111888	88818881	18881111	81818111	11881188	81118181	81888118	11181118	81188188
18181811	88118811	18111818	18818818	11811181	88181881	18888881	11111111	88811888	81111188	81818181	11888111	81181118	81888188	11188118
18118811	18181818	88111811	88181181	18811881	11818818	88811111	18881888	11118881	11888181	81118111	81811188	11188188	81188118	81881118
81811888	11888881	81111111	81888111	11181188	81188181	88118118	18111118	18188188	11811818	88181811	18818811	11111881	88818818	18881181
81118881	81811111	11881888	81181188	81888181	11188111	18181118	88118188	18118118	18811811	11818811	88181818	18888818	11111181	88811881
11881111	81111888	81818881	11188181	81188111	81881188	18118188	18188118	88111118	88188811	18811818	11811811	88811181	18881881	11118818
11818118	88181118	18818188	11111818	88811811	18888811	81811881	11888818	81111181	81881888	11188881	81181111	88118111	18111188	18188181
18811118	11818188	88188118	18881811	11118811	88811818	81118818	81811181	11881881	81188881	81881111	11181888	18181188	88118181	18118111
88188188	18818118	11811118	88818811	18881818	11111811	11881181	81111881	81818818	11181111	81181888	81888881	18118181	18188111	88111188
81881881	11188818	81181181	88111888	18118881	18181111	11818111	88181188	18818181	11118118	88811118	18888188	81811818	11881811	81118811
81188818	81881181	11181881	18188881	88111111	18111888	18811188	11818181	88188111	18881118	11118188	88818118	81111811	81818811	11881818
11181181	81181881	81888818	18111111	18181888	88118881	88188181	18818111	11811188	88818188	18888118	11111118	11888811	81111818	81811811
11118111	88811188	18888181	81818118	11881118	81118188	81881818	11181811	81188811	88111881	18118818	18181181	11811888	88188881	18811111
18881188	11118181	88818111	81111118	81818188	11888118	81181811	81888811	11181818	18188818	88111181	18111881	18818881	11811111	88181888
88818181	18888111	11111188	11888188	81118118	81811118	11188811	81181818	81881811	18111181	18181881	88118818	88181111	18811888	11818881

The magic square of order 15 given in Example 3.12 with 2-digits (1,8) is **universal** and **semi-magic** with **semi-magic sum**: $S_{15 \times 15}(1,8) := 711111104$. The blocks of order 3 are **semi-magicsquares** with different **semi-magic sums**.

• **8-Digits Cell: The Numbers 2 and 5 - Blocks of Order 5**

Example 3.13. *Let's consider a magic square of order 15 with 2-digits (2,5) given by*

22222225	25252525	25522522	52555525	55222555	22522252	22555225	52222255	52255552	55525222	22252222	25225255	25552525	52525522	55252552
52552522	55225525	22222555	25252225	25525252	52252255	55525552	22525222	22552252	52225225	52522525	55255522	22252552	25222222	25555255
25252555	25522225	52555252	55222522	22225525	22555222	52222252	52255225	55522255	22525552	25222552	25552222	52525255	55252525	22255522
55225252	22222522	25255525	25522555	52552225	55525225	22522255	22555552	52225222	52252252	55255255	22252525	25225522	25552552	52522222
25525525	52552555	55222225	22225252	25252522	52225552	52255222	55522252	22525225	22552255	25555522	52522552	55252222	22255255	25222525
22522222	22555255	52222525	52255522	55522552	22252225	25225252	25552522	52525525	55252555	22222252	25255225	25522255	52555552	55225222
52252525	55525522	22522552	22552222	52225255	52522522	55255525	22252555	25222225	25555252	52552255	55225552	22225222	25252252	25525225
22552552	52222222	52255255	55522525	22525522	25222555	25552225	52525252	55252522	22255525	25255222	25522252	52555225	55222255	22225552
55525255	22522525	22555522	52222552	52252222	55255252	22225252	25225525	25552555	52522225	55225225	22222255	25255552	25525222	52552252
52225522	52252552	55522222	22525255	22552525	25555525	52522555	55252225	22255252	25222522	25525552	52555222	55222252	22225225	25252255
22252252	25225225	25552255	52525552	55255222	22222222	25255255	25522525	52555522	55222552	22522225	22555252	52222522	52255525	55522555
52522255	55255552	22255222	25222252	25555225	52552525	55225522	22222552	25252222	25525255	52252522	55525525	22225555	22552225	52225252
25225222	25552252	52525225	55252255	22255552	25252552	25522222	52555255	55222525	22225522	22525555	52222225	52255252	55522522	22525525
55255225	22252255	25225552	25555222	52522252	55225255	22222525	25255522	25522552	52552222	55525252	22522522	22555525	52222555	52252225
25555552	52525222	55252252	22255225	25222255	25525522	52552552	55222222	22225255	25252525	52225525	52252555	55522225	22525252	22552522

The magic square of order 15 given in Example 3.13 with 2-digits (2,5) is **universal** and **semi-magic** with **semi-magic** sums: $S_{15 \times 15}(2, 5) := 566666661$ and $S_{15 \times 15}(2, 5) := 599999994$. The sum $S_{15 \times 15}(2, 5) := 599999994$ refers to **mirror looking** version. Blocks of order 5 are **pandiagonal** magic squares with different magic sums.

• **8-Digits Cell: The Numbers 2 and 5 - Blocks of Order 3**

Example 3.14. *Let's consider a magic square of order 15 with 2-digits (2,5) with blocks of order 3:*

55222525	25222522	25255522	22522552	55255525	25522252	22222555	55525552	25552222	52525222	22552255	52222525	52555225	22252225	52255255
25252522	55225522	25222525	25525525	22522252	55252552	25555552	22222222	55522555	52222255	52525252	22555222	52252225	52555255	22255225
25225522	25252525	55222522	55252252	25522552	22525525	55522222	25552555	22225552	22555252	52225222	52522255	22255255	52255225	52552225
52522555	22555552	52222222	52555222	22252255	52255252	55225225	25222225	25255255	22522525	55252522	25525522	22222552	55255255	25552252
52225552	52522222	22552555	52252255	52555252	22255222	25252225	55225255	25225225	25522522	22525522	55252525	25555525	22222252	55522552
22552222	52222555	52525552	22255252	52255222	52552255	25225255	25255225	55222225	55255522	25522525	22522522	55522252	25552552	22225525
22525225	55252225	25525255	22222525	55522522	25555522	52522552	22555525	52222252	52552555	22255552	52252222	55225222	25222255	25255252
25522225	22525255	55255225	25552522	22225522	55522525	52225525	52522252	22552552	52255552	52552222	22252555	25252255	55225252	25225222
55255255	25525225	22522225	55525522	25552525	22222522	22552252	52222552	52525525	22252222	52252555	52555552	25225252	25255222	55222255
52552552	22255525	52252252	55222555	25225552	25252222	22525222	55252255	25525252	22225225	55522225	25555255	52522525	22552522	52225522
52255525	52552252	22252552	25255552	55222222	25222555	25522255	22525252	55255222	25552225	22225255	55525225	52222522	52525522	22552525
22252252	52252552	52555525	25222222	25252555	55225552	55255252	25525222	22522255	55525255	25555225	22222225	22555522	52222525	52522522
22225222	55522255	25555252	52525225	22552225	52225255	52552525	22252522	52255522	55222552	25225525	25252252	22522555	55255552	25522222
25552255	22225252	55525222	52222225	52525255	22555225	52252522	52555522	22252525	25255525	55222252	25222552	25525552	22522222	55252555
55525252	25555222	22222255	22555255	52225225	52522225	22255522	52252525	52552522	25222252	25252552	55225525	55252222	25522555	22525552

The magic square of order 15 given in Example 3.14 with 2-digits (2,5) is **universal** and **semi-magic** with **semi-magic** sums: $S_{15 \times 15}(2, 5) := 566666661$ and $S_{15 \times 15}(2, 5) := 599999994$. The sum $S_{15 \times 15}(2, 5) := 599999994$ refers to **mirror looking** version. Blocks of order 3 are **semi-magic** squares with different **semi-magic** sums.

• **8-Digits Cell: The Numbers 6 and 9 - Blocks of Order 5**

Example 3.15. *Let's consider a magic square of order 15 with 2-digits (6,9) is given by*

6666669	69699696	69966966	96999969	99666999	66966696	66999669	96666699	96699996	99969666	66696969	69669966	69996996	96969999	99699699
96996966	99669969	66666999	69696669	69969696	96696699	99969996	66969666	66996696	96669669	96966996	99699999	66699699	69666969	69999966
69696999	69966669	96999696	99666966	66669969	66999666	96666696	96699669	99966699	66969996	69669699	69996969	96969966	99696996	66699999
99669696	66666966	69699969	69966999	96996669	99969669	66966699	66999996	96669666	96696696	99699966	66696996	69669999	69999699	96966969
69969969	96996999	99666669	66669696	69696966	96669996	96699666	99966696	66969669	66996699	69999999	96969699	99696969	66699966	69666996
66966969	66999966	96666996	96699999	99969699	66696669	69669696	69996966	96969969	99696999	66666696	69699669	69966699	96999996	99669666
96696996	99969999	66969699	66996969	96669966	96966966	99699969	66696999	69666669	69999696	96996699	99669996	66669666	69696696	69969669
66999699	96666969	96699966	99966996	66969999	69666999	69996669	96969696	99696966	66699969	69699666	69966696	96999669	99666699	66669996
99969966	66966996	66999999	96669699	96696969	99699696	66696966	69669969	69996999	96966669	99669669	66666699	69699996	69969666	96996696
96669999	96699699	99966969	66969966	66996996	69999969	96966999	99696669	66699696	69666966	69969996	96999666	99666696	66669669	69696699
66696696	69669669	69996699	96969996	99699666	66666969	69699966	69966996	96999999	99669699	66966669	66999696	96666966	96699969	99966999
96966699	99699996	66699666	69666696	69999669	96996996	99669999	66669699	69696969	69969966	96696966	99969969	66966999	66996669	96669696
69669666	69996696	96969669	99696699	66699996	69699699	69966969	96999966	99666996	66669999	66996999	96666669	96699696	99966966	66969969
99699669	66696699	69669996	69999666	96966696	99669966	66666996	69699999	69969699	96996969	99969696	66966966	66999699	96666999	96696669
69999996	96969666	99696696	66699669	69666699	69969999	96999699	99666969	66669966	69696996	96669969	96696999	99966669	66969696	66996966

The *semi-magic* square of order 15 given in Example 3.15 with 2-digits (6,9) is *universal* and *semi-magic* with *semi-magic* sums: $S_{15 \times 15}(6, 9) := 1233336654$. Blocks of order 5 are *pandiagonal* magic squares with different magic sums.

• **8-Digits Cell: The Numbers 6 and 9 - Blocks of Order 3**

Example 3.16. *Let's consider a magic square of order 15 with 2-digits (6,9) with blocks of order 3:*

99666996	69666969	69699969	96999669	66696966	96699699	66669696	99966696	69999966	96966999	66999996	96666699	66969666	99699999	69966669
69696969	99669969	69666996	96696966	96999699	66699669	69996696	66669966	99969696	96669996	96966699	66996999	69969999	66966669	99699666
69669969	69696996	99666969	66699699	96699669	96996966	99969966	69999696	66666696	66996699	96666999	96969996	99696669	69969666	66969999
96969696	66996696	96669966	66966999	99699996	69966699	99669666	69669999	69696669	96996996	66696969	96699969	66669669	99966966	69999699
96666696	96969966	66999696	69969996	66966699	99696999	69699999	99666669	69669666	96696969	96999969	66696996	69996966	66669699	99969669
66999966	96669696	96966696	99696699	69966999	66969996	69666669	69699666	99669999	66699969	96696996	96996969	99969699	69996669	66669666
96999666	66699999	96696669	66666996	99966969	69999969	96969669	66996966	96669699	66969696	99696696	69969966	99666999	69669996	69696699
96699999	96996669	66699666	69996969	66669969	99966996	96666966	96969699	66999669	69966696	66969966	99699696	69699996	99666699	69666999
66696669	96699666	96999999	99969969	69996996	66666969	66999699	96669669	96969666	99699966	69969696	66966696	69666699	69696999	99669996
66969669	99696966	69969699	99669696	69666696	69699966	96996999	66699996	96696699	66669666	99969999	69996669	96966996	66996969	96669969
69966966	66969699	99699669	69696696	99669966	69669696	96699996	96996699	66696999	69999999	66666669	99969666	96666969	96969969	66996996
99699699	69969669	66966966	69669966	69699696	99666696	66696699	96696999	96999996	99966669	69999666	66669999	66999969	96666996	96966969
66666999	99969996	69996699	96969666	66999999	96666669	66966996	99696969	69969969	99669669	69666966	69699699	96999696	66696696	96699966
69999996	66666699	99966999	96669999	96966669	66999666	69966969	66969969	99696996	69696966	99669699	69669669	96696696	96999966	66699696
99966699	69996999	66669996	66996669	96669666	96969999	99699969	69966996	66966969	69669699	69699669	99666966	66699966	96699696	96996696

The *semi-magic* square of order 15 given in Example 3.16 with 2-digits (6,9) is *upside-down* and *semi-magic* with *semi-magic* sums: $S_{15 \times 15}(6, 9) := 1233336654$. Blocks of order 3 are *semi-magic* squares with different *semi-magic* sums.

3.3.2 Water Reflection and Magic Squares

bullet 4-Digits Magic Squares

In this subsection we shall bring four magic squares of order 15 of 4-digits (2,3,5,8), (1,2,3,5), (0,2,3,5) and (0,1,3,8).

Example 3.17. *Let's consider a magic square of order 15 with 4-digits (2,3,5,8) given by*

2223	3558	3832	8285	8352	2525	2855	5328	5588	8853	2322	3282	5235	5883	8538
8232	8385	2252	3523	3858	5528	8888	2553	2825	5355	5835	8583	2338	3222	5282
3552	3823	8258	8332	2285	2853	5325	5555	8828	2588	3238	5222	5882	8535	2383
8358	2232	3585	3852	8223	8855	2528	2888	5353	5525	8582	2335	3283	5238	5822
3885	8252	8323	2258	3532	5388	5553	8825	2555	2828	5283	5838	8522	2382	3235
2522	2882	5335	5583	8838	2323	3258	5232	5885	8552	2225	3555	3828	8288	8353
5535	8883	2538	2822	5382	5832	8585	2352	3223	5258	8228	8388	2253	3525	3855
2838	5322	5582	8835	2583	3252	5223	5858	8532	2385	3553	3825	8255	8328	2288
8882	2535	2883	5338	5522	8558	2332	3285	5252	5823	8355	2228	3588	3853	8225
5383	5538	8822	2582	2835	5285	5852	8523	2358	3232	3888	8253	8325	2255	3528
2325	3255	5228	5888	8553	2222	3582	3835	8283	8338	2523	2858	5332	5585	8852
5828	8588	2353	3225	5255	8235	8383	2238	3522	3882	5532	8885	2552	2823	5358
3253	5225	5855	8528	2388	3538	3822	8282	8335	2283	2852	5323	5558	8832	2585
8555	2328	3288	5253	5825	8382	2235	3583	3838	8222	8858	2532	2885	5352	5523
5288	5853	8525	2355	3228	3883	8238	8322	2282	3535	5385	5552	8823	2558	2832

The above *semi-magic* square of order 15 with digits is (2,3,5,8) is *water reflexive* with different *semi-magic* sums. The blocks of order 5 are *pandiagonal* magic squares with different magic sums. Let's see below few more examples.

Example 3.18. *Let's replace 8 by 1 in Example 3.17, we get*

2223	3551	3132	1215	1352	2525	2155	5321	5511	1153	2322	3212	5235	5113	1531
1232	1315	2252	3523	3151	5521	1111	2553	2125	5355	5135	1513	2331	3222	5212
3552	3123	1251	1332	2215	2153	5325	5555	1121	2511	3231	5222	5112	1535	2313
1351	2232	3515	3152	1223	1155	2521	2111	5353	5525	1512	2335	3213	5231	5122
3115	1252	1323	2251	3532	5311	5553	1125	2555	2121	5213	5131	1522	2312	3235
2522	2112	5335	5513	1131	2323	3251	5232	5115	1552	2225	3555	3121	1211	1353
5535	1113	2531	2122	5312	5132	1515	2352	3223	5251	1221	1311	2253	3525	3155
2131	5322	5512	1135	2513	3252	5223	5151	1532	2315	3553	3125	1255	1321	2211
1112	2535	2113	5331	5522	1551	2332	3215	5252	5123	1355	2221	3511	3153	1225
5313	5531	1122	2512	2135	5215	5152	1523	2351	3232	3111	1253	1325	2255	3521
2325	3255	5221	5111	1553	2222	3512	3135	1213	1331	2523	2151	5332	5515	1152
5121	1511	2353	3225	5255	1235	1313	2231	3522	3112	5532	1115	2552	2123	5351
3253	5225	5155	1521	2311	3531	3122	1212	1335	2213	2152	5323	5551	1132	2515
1555	2321	3211	5253	5125	1312	2235	3513	3131	1222	1151	2532	2115	5352	5523
5211	5153	1525	2355	3221	3113	1231	1322	2212	3535	5315	5552	1123	2551	2132

The above semi-magic square is water reflexive with equal semi-magic sums. The blocks of order 5 are pandiagonal magic squares with different magic sums.

Example 3.19. Let's replace 1 by 0 in Example 3.18, we get

2223	3550	3032	0205	0352	2525	2055	5320	5500	0053	2322	3202	5235	5003	0530
0232	0305	2252	3523	3050	5520	0000	2553	2025	5355	5035	0503	2330	3222	5202
3552	3023	0250	0332	2205	2053	5325	5555	0020	2500	3230	5222	5002	0535	2303
0350	2232	3505	3052	0223	0055	2520	2000	5353	5525	0502	2335	3203	5230	5022
3005	0252	0323	2250	3532	5300	5553	0025	2555	2020	5203	5030	0522	2302	3235
2522	2002	5335	5503	0030	2323	3250	5232	5005	0552	2225	3555	3020	0200	0353
5535	0003	2530	2022	5302	5032	0505	2352	3223	5250	0220	0300	2253	3525	3055
2030	5322	5502	0035	2503	3252	5223	5050	0532	2305	3553	3025	0255	0320	2200
0002	2535	2003	5330	5522	0550	2332	3205	5252	5023	0355	2220	3500	3053	0225
5303	5530	0022	2502	2035	5205	5052	0523	2350	3232	3000	0253	0325	2255	3520
2325	3255	5220	5000	0553	2222	3502	3035	0203	0330	2523	2050	5332	5505	0052
5020	0500	2353	3225	5255	0235	0303	2230	3522	3002	5532	0005	2552	2023	5350
3253	5225	5055	0520	2300	3530	3022	0202	0335	2203	2052	5323	5550	0032	2505
0555	2320	3200	5253	5025	0302	2235	3503	3030	0222	0050	2532	2005	5352	5523
5200	5053	0525	2355	3220	3003	0230	0322	2202	3535	5305	5552	0023	2550	2032

The above semi-magic square is water reflexive with semi-magic sum $S_{15 \times 15}(0, 2, 3, 5) := 41107$.

Example 3.20. Let's replace 2 by 1 and 5 by 8 in Example 3.19, we get

1113	3880	3031	0108	0381	1818	1088	8310	8800	0083	1311	3101	8138	8003	0830
0131	0308	1181	3813	3080	8810	0000	1883	1018	8388	8038	0803	1330	3111	8101
3881	3013	0180	0331	1108	1083	8318	8888	0010	1800	3130	8111	8001	0838	1303
0380	1131	3808	3081	0113	0088	1810	1000	8383	8818	0801	1338	3103	8130	8011
3008	0181	0313	1180	3831	8300	8883	0018	1888	1010	8103	8030	0811	1301	3138
1811	1001	8338	8803	0030	1313	3180	8131	8008	0881	1118	3888	3010	0100	0383
8838	0003	1830	1011	8301	8031	0808	1381	3113	8180	0110	0300	1183	3818	3088
1030	8311	8801	0038	1803	3181	8113	8080	0831	1308	3883	3018	0188	0310	1100
0001	1838	1003	8330	8811	0880	1331	3108	8181	8013	0388	1110	3800	3083	0118
8303	8830	0011	1801	1038	8108	8081	0813	1380	3131	3000	0183	0318	1188	3810
1318	3188	8110	8000	0883	1111	3801	3038	0103	0330	1813	1080	8331	8808	0081
8010	0800	1383	3118	8188	0138	0303	1130	3811	3001	8831	0008	1881	1013	8380
3183	8118	8088	0810	1300	3830	3011	0101	0338	1103	1081	8313	8880	0031	1808
0888	1310	3100	8183	8018	0301	1138	3803	3030	0111	0080	1831	1008	8381	8813
8100	8083	0818	1388	3110	3003	0130	0311	1101	3838	8308	8881	0013	1880	1031

The above semi-magic square is water reflexive with semi-magic sum $S_{15 \times 15}(0, 1, 3, 8) := 49995$.

Finally, we have four semi-magic squares of order 15 with 4-digits (2,3,5,8), (1,2,3,5), (0,2,3,5) and (0,1,3,8) results in water reflection semi-magic squares with same semi-magic sums except the first with digits (2,3,5,8). The blocks of order 5 are pandiagonal magic squares with different magic sums.

bullet 3-Digits Magic Squares

In this subsection we shall bring four magic squares of order 15 with 3-digits (2,3,5), (1,3,8), (0,3,8) and (0,1,3).

Example 3.21. *Let's consider a magic square of order 15 with 4-digits (2,3,5) given by*

222225	322533	332255	535553	552333	232232	233522	335233	522555	555335	225222	255535	333322	533552	553332
535255	552553	222333	322225	332533	522233	555555	232335	233232	335522	533322	553552	225332	255222	333535
322333	332225	535533	552255	222553	233335	335232	522522	555233	232555	255332	333222	533535	553322	225552
552533	222255	322553	332333	535225	555522	232233	233555	335335	522232	553535	225322	255552	333332	533222
332553	535333	552225	222533	322255	335555	522335	555232	232522	233233	333552	533332	553222	225535	255322
232222	233535	335322	522552	555332	225225	255533	333255	533553	553333	222232	322522	332233	535555	552335
522322	555552	232332	233222	335535	533255	553553	225333	255225	333533	535233	552555	222335	322232	332522
233332	335222	522535	555322	232552	255333	333225	533533	553255	225553	322335	332232	535522	552233	222555
555535	232322	233552	335332	522222	553533	225255	255553	333333	533225	552522	222233	322555	332335	535232
335552	522332	555222	232535	233322	333553	533333	553225	225533	255255	332555	535335	552232	222522	322233
225232	255522	333233	533555	553335	222222	322535	332322	535552	552332	232225	233533	335255	522553	555333
533233	553555	225335	255232	333522	535322	552552	222332	322222	332535	522255	555553	232333	233225	335533
255335	333232	533522	553233	225555	322332	332222	535535	552322	222552	233333	335225	522533	555255	232553
553522	225233	255555	333335	533232	552535	222322	322552	332332	535222	555533	232255	233553	335333	522225
333555	533335	553232	225522	255233	332552	535332	552222	222535	322322	335553	522333	555225	232533	233255

Thus, the above *semi-magic* square of order 15 with digits is (2,3,5) is *water reflexive* with different *semi-magic* sum. The blocks of order 5 are *pandiagonal* magic squares with different magic sums. Let's see below few more examples.

Example 3.22. *Let's replace 8 by 1 in Example 3.21, we get*

111118	311833	331188	838883	881333	131131	133811	338133	811888	888338	118111	188838	333311	833881	883331
838188	881883	111333	311118	331833	811133	888888	131338	133131	338811	833311	883881	118331	188111	333838
311333	331118	838833	881188	111883	133338	338131	811811	888133	131888	188331	333111	833838	883311	118881
881833	111188	311883	331333	838118	888811	131133	133888	338338	811131	883838	118311	188881	333331	833111
331883	838333	881118	111833	311188	338888	811338	888131	131811	133133	333881	833331	883111	118838	188311
131111	133838	338311	811881	888331	118118	188833	333188	833883	883333	111131	311811	331133	838888	881338
811311	888881	131331	133111	338838	833188	883883	118333	188118	333833	838133	881888	111338	311131	331811
133331	338111	811838	888311	131881	188333	333118	833833	883188	118883	311338	331131	838811	881133	111888
888838	131311	133881	338331	811111	883833	118188	188883	333333	833118	881811	111133	311888	331338	838131
338881	811331	888111	131838	133311	333883	833333	883118	118833	188188	331888	838338	881131	111811	311133
118131	188811	333133	833888	883338	111111	311838	331311	838881	881331	131118	133833	338188	811883	888333
833133	883888	118338	188131	333811	838311	881881	111331	311111	331838	811188	888883	131333	133118	338833
188338	333131	833811	883133	118888	311331	331111	838838	881311	111881	133333	338118	811833	888188	131883
883811	118133	188888	333338	833131	881838	111311	311881	331331	838111	888833	131188	133883	338333	811118
333888	833338	883131	118811	188133	331881	838331	881111	111838	311311	338883	811333	888118	131833	133188

The semi-magic sum of above semi-magic square is $S_{15 \times 15}(1, 3, 8) := 7135128$. Thus, the above semi-magic square is water reflexive with equal semi-magic sums. The blocks of order 5 are pandiagonal magic squares with different magic sums.

Example 3.23. Let's replace 1 by 0 in Example 3.22, we get

000008	300833	330088	838883	880333	030030	033800	338033	800888	888338	008000	088838	333300	833880	883330
838088	880883	000333	300008	330833	800033	888888	030338	033030	338800	833300	883880	008330	088000	333838
300333	330008	838833	880088	000883	033338	338030	800800	888033	030888	088330	333000	833838	883300	008880
880833	000088	300883	330333	838008	888800	030033	033888	338338	800030	883838	008300	088880	333330	833000
330883	838333	880008	000833	300088	338888	800338	888030	030800	033033	333880	833330	883000	008838	088300
030000	033838	338300	800880	888330	008008	088833	333088	833883	883333	000030	300800	330033	838888	880338
800300	888880	030330	033000	338838	833088	883883	008333	088008	333833	838033	880888	000338	300030	330800
033330	338000	800838	888300	030880	088333	333008	833833	883088	008883	300338	330030	838800	880033	000888
888838	030300	033880	338330	800000	883833	008088	088883	333333	833008	880800	000033	300888	330338	838030
338880	800330	888000	030838	033300	333883	833333	883008	008833	088088	330888	838338	880030	000800	300033
008030	088800	333033	833888	883338	000000	300838	330300	838880	880330	030008	033833	338088	800883	888333
833033	883888	008338	088030	333800	838300	880880	000330	300000	330838	800088	888883	030333	033008	338833
088338	333030	833800	883033	008888	300330	330000	838838	880300	000880	033333	338008	800833	888088	030883
883800	008033	088888	333338	833030	880838	000300	300880	330330	838000	888833	030088	033883	338333	800008
333888	833338	883030	008800	088033	330880	838330	880000	000838	300300	338883	800333	888008	030833	033088

The semi-magic sum of above semi-magic square is $S_{15 \times 15}(0, 3, 8) := 6588582$.

Example 3.24. Let's replace 8 by 1 in Example 3.22, we get

000001	300133	330011	131113	110333	030030	033100	331033	100111	111331	001000	011131	333300	133110	113330
131011	110113	000333	300001	330133	100033	111111	030331	033030	331100	133300	113110	001330	011000	333131
300333	330001	131133	110011	000113	033331	331030	100100	111033	030111	011330	333000	133131	113300	001110
110133	000011	300113	330333	131001	111100	030033	033111	331331	100030	113131	001300	011110	333330	133000
330113	131333	110001	000133	300011	331111	100331	111030	030100	033033	333110	133330	113000	001131	011300
030000	033131	331300	100110	111330	001001	011133	333011	133113	113333	000030	300100	330033	131111	110331
100300	111110	030330	033000	331131	133011	113113	001333	011001	333133	131033	110111	000331	300030	330100
033330	331000	100131	111300	030110	011333	333001	133133	113011	001113	300331	330030	131100	110033	000111
111131	030300	033110	331330	100000	113133	001011	011113	333333	133001	110100	000033	300111	330331	131030
331110	100330	111000	030131	033300	333113	133333	113001	001133	011011	330111	131331	110030	000100	300033
001030	011100	333033	133111	113331	000000	300131	330300	131110	110330	030001	033133	331011	100113	111333
133033	113111	001331	011030	333100	131300	110110	000330	300000	330131	100011	111113	030333	033001	331133
011331	333030	133100	113033	001111	300330	330000	131131	110300	000110	033333	331001	100133	111011	030113
113100	001033	011111	333331	133030	110131	000300	300110	330330	131000	111133	030011	033113	331333	100001
333111	133331	113030	001100	011033	330110	131330	110000	000131	300300	331113	100333	111001	030133	033011

The semi-magic sum of above semi-magic square is $S_{15 \times 15}(0, 1, 3) := 2069067$.

Finally, we have four **semi-magic** squares of order 15 with 4-digits (2,3,5), (1,3,8), (0,3,8) and (0,1,3) results in **water reflection semi-magic** squares with same **semi-magic** sums except the first with digits (2,3,5). The blocks of order 5 are **pandiagonal** magic squares with different magic sums.

bullet 2-Digits Magic Squares: Blocks of Order 5

In this subsection, we shall bring four magic squares of order 15 with 2-digits (3,8), (1,3) and (0,3).

Example 3.25. *Let's consider a magic square of order 15 with 2-digits (3,8) given by*

3333338	38388383	38833833	83888838	88333888	33833383	33888338	83333388	83388883	88838333	33383333	38338388	38883838	83838833	88383883
83883833	88338838	33333888	38383338	38838383	83383388	88838883	33838333	33883383	83338338	83833838	88388833	33383883	38333333	38888388
38383888	38833338	83888383	88333833	33338838	33888333	83333383	83388338	88833888	33838883	38333883	38883333	83838388	88383838	33388833
88338383	33333833	38388838	38833888	83883338	88838338	33833388	33888883	83338333	83383383	88388388	33383838	38338833	38883883	83833333
38838838	83883888	88333338	33338383	38383833	83338883	83388333	88833383	33838338	33883388	38888833	83833883	88383333	33388388	38333838
33833333	33888388	83333838	83388833	88833883	33383338	38338383	38883833	83838838	88383888	33333833	38388338	38833888	83888883	88338333
83383838	88838833	33833883	33883333	83338388	83833833	88388838	33383888	38333338	38888383	83883388	88338883	33338333	38383383	38838338
33883883	83333333	83388388	88833838	33838833	38333888	38883338	83838383	88383833	33388838	38388333	38833383	83888338	88333388	33338883
88838388	33833838	33888833	83333883	83383333	88388383	33383833	38338838	38883888	83833338	88338338	33333888	38388883	38838333	83883383
83338833	83383883	88833333	33838388	33883838	38888838	83833888	88383338	33388383	38333833	38838883	83888333	88333383	33338338	38383388
33383383	38338338	38883388	83838883	88388333	33333333	38388388	38833838	83888833	88333883	33833338	33888383	83333833	83388838	88833888
83833388	88388883	33388333	38333383	38888338	83883838	88338833	33333883	38383333	38838388	83383833	88838838	33833888	33883338	83338383
38338333	38883383	83838338	88383388	33388883	38383883	38833333	83888388	88333838	33338833	33883888	83333338	83388383	88833833	33838838
88388338	33383388	38338883	38888333	83833383	88338388	33333838	38388833	38833883	83883333	88838383	33833833	33888838	83333888	83383338
38888883	83838333	88383383	33388338	38333388	38838833	83883883	88333333	33338388	38383838	83338838	83383888	88833338	33838383	33883833

The above *semi-magic* square of order 15 with digits is (3,8) is *water reflexive* with different *semi-magic* sum. The blocks of order 5 are *pandiagonal* magic squares with different magic sums. Let's see below few more examples.

Example 3.26. Let's replace 8 by 1 in Example 3.25, we get

3333331	31311313	31133133	13111131	11333111	33133313	33111331	13333311	13311113	11131333	33313333	31331311	31113131	13131133	11313113
13113133	11331131	33333111	31313331	31131313	13313311	11131113	33131333	33113313	13331331	13133131	11311133	33313113	31333333	31111311
31313111	31133331	13111313	11333133	33331131	33111333	13333313	13311331	11133311	33131113	31333113	31113333	13131311	11313131	33311133
11331313	33333133	31311131	31133111	13113331	11131331	33133311	33111113	13331333	13313313	11311311	33313131	31331133	31113113	13133333
31131131	13113111	11333331	33331313	31313133	13331113	13311333	11133313	33131331	33113311	31111133	13133113	11313333	33311311	31333131
33133333	33111311	13333131	13311133	11133113	33313331	31331313	31113133	13131131	11313111	33333313	31311331	31133311	13111113	11331333
13313131	11131133	33133113	33113333	13331311	13133133	11311131	33313111	31333331	31111313	13113311	11331113	33331333	31313313	31131331
33113113	13333333	13311311	11133131	33131133	31333111	31113331	13131313	11313133	33311131	31311333	31133313	13111331	11333311	33331113
11131311	33133131	33111133	13333113	13313333	11311313	33313133	31331131	31113111	13133331	11331331	33333311	31311113	31131333	13113313
13331133	13313113	11133333	33131311	33113131	31111131	13133111	11313331	33311313	31333133	31131113	13111333	11333313	33331331	31313311
33313313	31331331	31113311	13131113	11311333	33333333	31311311	31133131	13111133	11333113	33133331	33111313	13333133	13311131	11133111
13133311	11311113	33311333	31333313	31111331	13113131	11331133	33333113	31313333	31131311	13313133	11131131	33133111	33113331	13331313
31331333	31113313	13131331	11313311	33311113	31313113	31133333	13111311	11333131	33331133	33113111	13333331	13311313	11133133	33131131
11311331	33313311	31331113	31111333	13133313	11331311	33333131	31311133	31133113	13113333	11131313	33133133	33111131	13333111	13313331
31111113	13131333	11313313	33311331	31333311	31131133	13113113	11333333	33331311	31313131	13331131	13313111	11133331	33131313	33113133

The *semi-magic* sum of above *semi-magic* square is $S_{15 \times 15}(1, 3) := 344444441$. The above *semi-magic* square is *water reflexive* with equal *semi-magic* sums. The blocks of order 5 are *pandiagonal* magic squares with different magic sums.

Example 3.27. *Let's replace 1 by 0 in Example 3.26, we get*

3333330	30300303	30033033	03000030	00333000	33033303	33000330	03333300	03300003	00030333	33303333	30330300	30003030	03030033	00303003
03003033	00330030	33333000	30303330	30030303	03303300	00030003	33030333	33003303	03330330	03033030	00300033	33303003	30333333	30000300
30303000	30033330	03000303	00333033	33330030	33000333	03333303	03300330	00033300	33030003	30333003	30003333	03030300	00303030	33300033
00330303	33333033	30300030	30033000	03003330	00030330	33033300	33000003	03330333	03303303	00300300	33303030	30330033	30003003	03033333
30030030	03003000	00333330	33330303	30303033	03330003	03300333	00033303	33030330	33003300	30000033	03033003	00303333	33300300	30333030
33033333	33000300	03333030	03300033	00033003	33303330	30330303	30003033	03030030	00303000	33333033	30300330	30033300	03000003	00330333
03303030	00030033	33033003	33003333	03330300	03033033	00300030	33303000	30333330	30000303	03003300	00330003	33330333	30303303	30030330
33003003	03333333	03300300	00033030	33030033	30333000	30003330	03030303	00303033	33300030	30300333	30033303	03000330	00333300	33330003
00030300	33033030	33000033	03333003	03303333	00300303	33303033	30330030	30003000	03033330	00330330	33333000	30300003	30030333	03003303
03330033	03303003	00033333	33030300	33003030	30000030	03033000	00303330	33300303	30333033	30030003	03000333	00333303	33330330	30303300
33303303	30330330	30003300	03030003	00300333	33333333	30300300	30033030	03000033	00333003	33033330	33000303	03333033	03300030	00033000
03033300	00300003	33300333	30333303	30000330	03003030	00330033	33333003	30303333	30030300	03303033	00030030	33033000	33003330	03330303
30330333	30003303	03030330	00303300	33300003	30303003	30033333	03000300	00333030	33330033	33003000	03333330	03300303	00033033	33030030
00300330	33303300	30330003	30000333	03033303	00330300	33333030	30300033	30033003	03003333	00030303	33033033	33000030	03333000	03303330
30000003	03030333	00303303	33300330	30333300	30030033	03003003	00333333	33330300	30303030	03330030	03303000	00033330	33030303	33003033

The *semi-magic* sum of above *semi-magic* square is $S_{15 \times 15}(0,3) := 266666664$.

Finally, we have three **semi-magic** squares of order 15 with 2-digits (3,8), (1,3) and (0,3) results in **water reflection semi-magic** squares with same **semi-magic** sums. The blocks of order 5 are **pandiagonal** magic squares with different magic sums.

bullet 2-Digits Magic Squares: Blocks of Order 3

In this subsection, we shall bring four magic squares of order 15 with 2-digits (3,8), (1,3) and (0,3). Here instead of blocks of order 5, we have blocks of order 3 as **semi-magic** squares of order 3.

Example 3.28. *Let's consider a magic square of order 15 with 2-digits (3,8) given by*

8833838	3833833	3838883	3383883	8838883	3883383	3333888	8883883	3888333	8383833	3388388	8333838	8388838	3383338	8338838
3838833	8833883	3833838	3883883	3383383	8838883	3888883	3333333	8883888	8333388	8383838	3388833	8338338	8388838	3388338
3833883	3838388	8833833	8838383	3883883	3383883	8883333	3888388	3333883	3388838	8333833	8383388	3388388	8338838	8388338
8383888	3388883	8333333	8388833	3383388	8338838	8838338	3833338	3838838	3383838	8838383	3883883	3333883	8883883	3888338
8338883	8383333	3388388	8338388	8388838	3388333	3838338	8838388	3838338	3883833	3383883	8838388	3888838	3333383	8883883
3388333	8333888	8383883	3388838	8338833	8388388	3838388	3838838	8833338	8838883	3883838	3383833	8883383	3888388	3333883
3383838	8838338	3883838	3333838	8883833	3888883	8383883	3388838	8333383	8388388	3388883	8338333	8838333	3833388	3838838
3883338	3383838	8838838	3888383	3333883	8883838	8333883	8383383	3388388	8338883	8388333	3383888	3838388	8838383	3838333
8838838	3883838	3383338	8883883	3888388	3333833	3388383	8333883	8383888	3383333	8338388	8388883	3838383	3838833	8833388
8388883	3388838	8338383	8833888	3833883	3838333	3383833	8838388	3883838	3333838	8883338	3888838	8383838	3388383	8333883
8338883	8388383	3383883	3838883	8833333	3833888	3883388	3383838	8838833	3888338	3333838	8883838	8333833	8383883	3388388
3383838	8338383	8388838	3833333	3838888	8833883	8838838	3883833	3383388	8883838	3888838	3333338	3388883	8333838	8383833
3333833	8883388	3888838	8383838	3388338	8333888	8388388	3383833	8338883	8833883	3833888	3838383	3383888	8838883	3883333
3888388	3333838	8883833	8333338	8383888	3388838	8338383	8388883	3383838	3838883	8833383	3833883	3883888	3383333	8838388
8883838	3888833	3333388	3388838	8333838	8383338	3388883	8338388	8388383	3833383	3838883	8833883	8838333	3883888	3383883

The semi-magic sum of above semi-magic square is $S_{15 \times 15}(3, 8) := 888888880$.

Example 3.29. Let's replace 8 by 1 in Example 3.28, we get

11333131	31333133	31311133	33133113	11311131	31133313	33333111	11131113	31113333	13131333	33113311	13331313	13111331	33313331	13311311
31313133	11331133	31333131	31131131	33133313	11313113	31111113	33333333	11133111	13333311	13131313	33111333	13313331	13111311	33311331
31331133	31313131	11333133	11313313	31133113	33131131	11133333	31113111	33331113	33111313	13331333	13133311	33311311	13311331	13113331
13133111	33111113	13333333	13111333	33313311	13311313	11331331	31333331	31311311	33133131	11313133	31131133	33333113	11131131	31113313
13331113	13133333	33113111	13313311	13111313	33311333	31313331	11331311	31331331	31133133	33131133	11313131	31111131	33333313	11133113
33113333	13333111	13131113	33311313	13311333	13113311	31331311	31311331	11333331	11311133	31133131	33133133	11133313	31113113	33331131
33131331	11313331	31131311	33333131	11133133	31111133	13133113	33111131	13333313	13113111	33311113	13313333	11331333	31333311	31311313
31133331	33131311	11311331	31113133	33331133	11133131	13331131	13133313	33113113	13311113	13113333	33313111	31313311	11331313	31331333
11311311	31131331	33133331	11131133	31113131	33333133	33113313	13333113	13131131	33313333	13313111	13111113	31331313	31311333	11333311
13113113	33311131	13313313	11333111	31331113	31313333	33131333	11313311	31131313	33331331	11133331	31111311	13133131	33113133	13331133
13311131	13113313	33313113	31311113	11333333	31333111	31133311	33131313	11311333	31113331	33331311	11131331	13333133	13131133	33113131
33313313	13313113	13111131	31333333	31313111	11331113	11311313	31131333	33133311	11131311	31111331	33333331	33111133	13333131	13133133
33331333	11133311	31111313	13131331	33113331	13331311	13113131	33313133	13311133	11333113	31331131	31313313	33133111	11311113	31133333
31113311	33331313	11131333	13333331	13131311	33111331	13313133	13111133	33313131	31311131	11333313	31333113	31131113	33133333	11313111
11131313	31111333	33333311	33111311	13331331	13133331	33311133	13313131	13113133	31333313	31313113	11331131	11313333	31133111	33131113

The semi-magic sum of above semi-magic square is $S_{15 \times 15}(1, 3) := 344444441$.

Example 3.30. Let's replace 1 by 0 in Example 3.29, we get

00333030	30333033	30300033	33033003	00300030	30033303	33333000	00030003	30003333	03030333	33003300	03330303	03000330	33303330	03300300
30303033	00330033	30333030	30030030	33033303	00303003	30000003	33333333	00033000	03333300	03030303	33000333	03303330	03000300	33300330
30330033	30303030	00333033	00303303	30033003	33030030	00033333	30003000	33330003	33000303	03330333	03033300	33300300	03300330	03003330
03033000	33000003	03333333	03000333	33303300	03300303	00330330	30333330	30300300	33033030	00303033	30030033	33333003	00030030	30003303
03330003	03033333	33003000	03303300	03000303	33300333	30303330	00330300	30330330	30033033	33030033	00303030	30000030	33333303	00033003
33003333	03333000	03030003	33300303	03300333	03003300	30330300	30300330	00333330	00300033	30033030	33033033	00033303	30003003	33330030
33030330	00303330	30030300	33333030	00033033	30000033	03033003	33000030	03333303	03003000	33300003	03303333	00330333	30333300	30300303
30033330	33030300	00300330	30003033	33330033	00033030	03330030	03033303	33003003	03300003	03003333	33303000	30303300	00330303	30330333
00300300	30030330	33033330	00030033	30003030	33333033	33003303	03333003	03030030	33303333	03303000	03000003	30330303	30300333	00333300
03003003	33300030	03303303	00333000	30330003	30303333	33030333	00303300	30030303	33330330	00033330	30000300	03033030	33003033	03330033
03300030	03003303	33303003	30300003	00333333	30333000	30033300	33030303	00300333	30003330	33330300	00030330	03333033	03030033	33003030
33303303	03303003	03000030	30333333	30303000	00330003	00300303	30030333	33033300	00030300	30000330	33333330	33000033	03333030	03033033
33330333	00033300	30000303	03030330	33003330	03330300	03003030	33303033	03300033	00333003	30330030	30303303	33033000	00300003	30033333
30003300	33330303	00030333	03333330	03030300	33000330	03303033	03000033	33303030	30300030	00333303	30333003	30030003	33033333	00303000
00030303	30000333	33333300	33000300	03330330	03033330	33300033	03303030	03003033	30333303	30303003	00330030	00303333	30033000	33030003

The semi-magic sum of above semi-magic square is $S_{15 \times 15}(0,3) := 266666664$.

Finally, we have three semi-magic squares of order 15 with 2-digits (3,8), (1,3) and (0,3) results in water reflection semi-magic squares with same semi-magic sums. The blocks of order 3 are semi-magic squares with different semi-magic sums.

3.4 Self-Made Algebraic Magic Squares of Order 15

3.4.1 Equal Sum Magic Squares of Order 5

Below is are two results of a magic square order 15 made from the variables in such a way that blocks of orders 5 and 3 are of equal sums magic squares of order 5 and 3. In case of order 5 it is **pandiagonal**.

Result 1. Below is an algebraic magic square of order 15

A1	A2	S-A1-A2-A3-A4	A3	A4	A9	A10	S-A9-A10-A11-A12	A11	A12	A17	A18	S-A17-A18-A19-A20	A19	A20
A8-A2+A7	A5	A1+A2+A3+A4-A5-A6-A7	A6	S-A1-A3-A4-A8	A16-A10+A15	A13	A9+A10+A11+A12-A13-A14-A15	A14	S-A9-A11-A12-A16	A24-A18+A23	A21	A17+A18+A19+A20-A21-A22-A23	A22	S-A17-A19-A20-A24
A2+A3+A4-A5-A7	S-A1-A2-A3-A4+A6-A8	A7	A7-A2-A3+A5+A8	A1+A2+A3-A6-A7	A10+A11+A12-A13-A15	S-A9-A10-A11-A12+A14-A16	A15	A15-A10-A11+A13+A16	A9+A10+A11-A14-A15	A18+A19+A20-A21-A23	S-A17-A18-A19-A20+A22-A24	A23	A23-A18-A19+A21+A24	A17+A18+A19-A22-A23
A7-A3+A5	A1-A6+A8	A2+A3-A7	S-A1-A5-A7-A8	A7-A2+A6	A15-A11+A13	A9-A14+A16	A10+A11-A15	S-A9-A13-A15-A16	A15-A10+A14	A23-A19+A21	A17-A22+A24	A18+A19-A23	S-A17-A21-A23-A24	A23-A18+A22
S-A1-A4-A7-A8	A3+A4-A5	A7-A2-A3+A5+A6	A1+A2-A6	A8	S-A9-A12-A15-A16	A11+A12-A13	A15-A10-A11+A13+A14	A9+A10-A14	A16	S-A17-A20-A23-A24	A19+A20-A21	A23-A18-A19+A21+A22	A17+A18-A22	A24
A33	A34	S-A33-A34-A33-A36	A33	A36	A25	A26	S-A25-A26-A27-A28	A27	A28	A41	A42	S-A41-A42-A43-A44	A43	A44
A40-A34+A39	A37	A33+A34+A33+A36-A37-A38-A39	A38	S-A33-A33-A36-A40	A32-A26+A31	A29	A25+A26+A27+A28-A29-A30-A31	A30	S-A25-A27-A28-A32	A48-A42+A47	A45	A41+A42+A43+A44-A45-A46-A47	A46	S-A41-A43-A44-A48
A34+A33+A36-A37-A39	S-A33-A34-A33-A36+A38-A40	A39	A39-A34-A33+A37+A40	A33+A34+A33-A38-A39	A26+A27+A28-A29-A31	S-A25-A26-A27-A28+A30-A32	A31	A31-A26-A27+A29+A32	A25+A26+A27-A30-A31	A42+A43+A44-A45-A47	S-A41-A42-A43-A44+A46-A48	A47	A47-A42-A43+A45+A48	A41+A42+A43-A46-A47
A39-A33+A37	A33-A38+A40	A34+A33-A39	S-A33-A37-A39-A40	A39-A34+A38	A31-A27+A29	A25-A30+A32	A26+A27-A31	S-A25-A29-A31-A32	A31-A26+A30	A47-A43+A45	A41-A46+A48	A42+A43-A47	S-A41-A45-A47-A48	A47-A42+A46
S-A33-A36-A39-A40	A33+A36-A37	A39-A34-A33+A37+A38	A33+A34-A38	A40	S-A25-A28-A31-A32	A27+A28-A29	A31-A26-A27+A29+A30	A25+A26-A30	A32	S-A41-A44-A47-A48	A43+A44-A45	A47-A42-A43+A45+A46	A41+A42-A46	A48
A49	A50	S-A49-A50-A51-A52	A51	A52	A57	A58	S-A57-A58-A59-A60	A59	A60	A65	A66	S-A65-A66-A67-A68	A67	A68
A56-A50+A55	A53	A49+A50+A51+A52-A53-A54-A55	A54	S-A49-A51-A52-A56	A64-A58+A63	A61	A57+A58+A59+A60-A61-A62-A63	A62	S-A57-A59-A60-A64	A72-A66+A71	A69	A65+A66+A67+A68-A69-A70-A71	A70	S-A65-A67-A68-A72
A50+A51+A52-A53-A55	S-A49-A50-A51-A52+A54-A56	A55	A55-A50-A51+A53+A56	A49+A50+A51-A54-A55	A58+A59+A60-A61-A63	S-A57-A58-A59-A60+A62-A64	A63	A63-A58-A59+A61+A64	A57+A58+A59-A62-A63	A66+A67+A68-A69-A71	S-A65-A66-A67-A68+A70-A72	A71	A71-A66-A67+A69+A72	A65+A66+A67-A70-A71
A55-A51+A53	A49-A54+A56	A50+A51-A55	S-A49-A53-A55-A56	A55-A50+A54	A63-A59+A61	A57-A62+A64	A58+A59-A63	S-A57-A61-A63-A64	A63-A58+A62	A71-A67+A69	A65-A70+A72	A66+A67-A71	S-A65-A69-A71-A72	A71-A66+A70
S-A49-A52-A55-A56	A51+A52-A53	A55-A50-A51+A53+A54	A49+A50-A54	A56	S-A57-A60-A63-A64	A59+A60-A61	A63-A58-A59+A61+A62	A57+A58-A62	A64	S-A65-A68-A71-A72	A67+A68-A69	A71-A66-A67+A69+A70	A65+A66-A70	A72

• Details

It is constructed in such a way that each block of order 5 is a *pandiagonal* magic square of order 5. The letter *S* represents the sum of each block of order 5. The magic sum of order 15 is $3 \times S$. We call it a *self-made* as choosing any numbers for *A1* to *A72* and the magic sum, we always get a magic square of order 15. Sometimes we may call it as *algebraic magic square for reduced entries*. It requires only 72 entries instead of 225. See below two examples:

Example 3.31. Let's consider a following magic square based on the Result 1

mgc	15x15 https://numbers-magic.com/ https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/ ©IJT														228
11	14	14	17	20	35	38	-82	41	44	59	62	-178	65	68	228
47	23	-16	26	-4	71	47	8	50	-100	95	71	32	74	-196	228
-1	8	29	53	-13	23	-88	53	77	11	47	-184	77	101	35	228
35	17	2	-19	41	59	41	26	-115	65	83	65	50	-211	89	228
-16	14	47	-1	32	-112	38	71	23	56	-208	62	95	47	80	228
107	110	-364	107	116	83	86	-274	89	92	131	134	-466	137	140	228
143	119	74	122	-382	119	95	56	98	-292	167	143	104	146	-484	228
89	-370	125	155	77	71	-280	101	125	59	119	-472	149	173	107	228
137	113	92	-403	137	107	89	74	-307	113	155	137	122	-499	161	228
-400	104	149	95	128	-304	86	119	71	104	-496	134	167	119	152	228
155	158	-562	161	164	179	182	-658	185	188	203	206	-754	209	212	228
191	167	128	170	-580	215	191	152	194	-676	239	215	176	218	-772	228
143	-568	173	197	131	167	-664	197	221	155	191	-760	221	245	179	228
179	161	146	-595	185	203	185	170	-691	209	227	209	194	-787	233	228
-592	158	191	143	176	-688	182	215	167	200	-784	206	239	191	224	228
228	228	228	228	228	228	228	228	228	228	228	228	228	228	228	228

Each block of order 5 is *apandiagonal* magic square of order 5 with magic sum $S_{5 \times 5} := 76$ resulting in magic sum of order 15 as $S_{15 \times 15} := 228$.

Example 3.32. Let's consider a following magic square based on the Result 1

mgc	15x15 https://numbers-magic.com/ https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/ ©IJT														243
11	14	19	17	20	35	38	-77	41	44	59	62	-173	65	68	243
47	23	-16	26	1	71	47	8	50	-95	95	71	32	74	-191	243
-1	13	29	53	-13	23	-83	53	77	11	47	-179	77	101	35	243
35	17	2	-14	41	59	41	26	-110	65	83	65	50	-206	89	243
-11	14	47	-1	32	-107	38	71	23	56	-203	62	95	47	80	243
107	110	-359	107	116	83	86	-269	89	92	131	134	-461	137	140	243
143	119	74	122	-377	119	95	56	98	-287	167	143	104	146	-479	243
89	-365	125	155	77	71	-275	101	125	59	119	-467	149	173	107	243
137	113	92	-398	137	107	89	74	-302	113	155	137	122	-494	161	243
-395	104	149	95	128	-299	86	119	71	104	-491	134	167	119	152	243
155	158	-557	161	164	179	182	-653	185	188	203	206	-749	209	212	243
191	167	128	170	-575	215	191	152	194	-671	239	215	176	218	-767	243
143	-563	173	197	131	167	-659	197	221	155	191	-755	221	245	179	243
179	161	146	-590	185	203	185	170	-686	209	227	209	194	-782	233	243
-587	158	191	143	176	-683	182	215	167	200	-779	206	239	191	224	243
243	243	243	243	243	243	243	243	243	243	243	243	243	243	243	243

Each block of order 5 is *apandiagonal* magic square of order 5 with magic sum $S_{5 \times 5} := 81$ resulting in magic sum of order 15 as $S_{15 \times 15} := 243$.

3.4.2 Equal Sum Magic Squares of Order 3

Result 2. Below is an algebraic magic square of order 15

$a_1+a_2-S/3$	$2*S/3-a_2$	$2*S/3-a_1$	$a_3+a_4-S/3$	$2*S/3-a_4$	$2*S/3-a_3$	$a_5+a_6-S/3$	$2*S/3-a_6$	$2*S/3-a_5$	$a_7+a_8-S/3$	$2*S/3-a_8$	$2*S/3-a_7$	$a_9+a_{10}-S/3$	$2*S/3-a_{10}$	$2*S/3-a_9$
$4*S/3-2*a_1-a_2$	$S/3$	$2*a_1+a_2-2*S/3$	$4*S/3-2*a_3-a_4$	$S/3$	$2*a_3+a_4-2*S/3$	$4*S/3-2*a_5-a_6$	$S/3$	$2*a_5+a_6-2*S/3$	$4*S/3-2*a_7-a_8$	$S/3$	$2*a_7+a_8-2*S/3$	$4*S/3-2*a_9-a_{10}$	$S/3$	$2*a_9+a_{10}-2*S/3$
a_1	a_2	$S-a_1-a_2$	a_3	a_4	$S-a_3-a_4$	a_5	a_6	$S-a_5-a_6$	a_7	a_8	$S-a_7-a_8$	a_9	a_{10}	$S-a_9-a_{10}$
$a_{11}+a_{12}-S/3$	$2*S/3-a_{12}$	$2*S/3-a_{11}$	$a_{13}+a_{14}-S/3$	$2*S/3-a_{14}$	$2*S/3-a_{13}$	$a_{15}+a_{16}-S/3$	$2*S/3-a_{16}$	$2*S/3-a_{15}$	$a_{17}+a_{18}-S/3$	$2*S/3-a_{18}$	$2*S/3-a_{17}$	$a_{19}+a_{20}-S/3$	$2*S/3-a_{20}$	$2*S/3-a_{19}$
$4*S/3-2*a_{11}-a_{12}$	$S/3$	$2*a_{11}+a_{12}-2*S/3$	$4*S/3-2*a_{13}-a_{14}$	$S/3$	$2*a_{13}+a_{14}-2*S/3$	$4*S/3-2*a_{15}-a_{16}$	$S/3$	$2*a_{15}+a_{16}-2*S/3$	$4*S/3-2*a_{17}-a_{18}$	$S/3$	$2*a_{17}+a_{18}-2*S/3$	$4*S/3-2*a_{19}-a_{20}$	$S/3$	$2*a_{19}+a_{20}-2*S/3$
a_{11}	a_{12}	$S-a_{11}-a_{12}$	a_{13}	a_{14}	$S-a_{13}-a_{14}$	a_{15}	a_{16}	$S-a_{15}-a_{16}$	a_{17}	a_{18}	$S-a_{17}-a_{18}$	a_{19}	a_{20}	$S-a_{19}-a_{20}$
$a_{21}+a_{22}-S/3$	$2*S/3-a_{22}$	$2*S/3-a_{21}$	$a_{23}+a_{24}-S/3$	$2*S/3-a_{24}$	$2*S/3-a_{23}$	$a_{25}+a_{26}-S/3$	$2*S/3-a_{26}$	$2*S/3-a_{25}$	$a_{27}+a_{28}-S/3$	$2*S/3-a_{28}$	$2*S/3-a_{27}$	$a_{29}+a_{30}-S/3$	$2*S/3-a_{30}$	$2*S/3-a_{29}$
$4*S/3-2*a_{21}-a_{22}$	$S/3$	$2*a_{21}+a_{22}-2*S/3$	$4*S/3-2*a_{23}-a_{24}$	$S/3$	$2*a_{23}+a_{24}-2*S/3$	$4*S/3-2*a_{25}-a_{26}$	$S/3$	$2*a_{25}+a_{26}-2*S/3$	$4*S/3-2*a_{27}-a_{28}$	$S/3$	$2*a_{27}+a_{28}-2*S/3$	$4*S/3-2*a_{29}-a_{30}$	$S/3$	$2*a_{29}+a_{30}-2*S/3$
a_{21}	a_{22}	$S-a_{21}-a_{22}$	a_{23}	a_{24}	$S-a_{23}-a_{24}$	a_{25}	a_{26}	$S-a_{25}-a_{26}$	a_{27}	a_{28}	$S-a_{27}-a_{28}$	a_{29}	a_{30}	$S-a_{29}-a_{30}$
$a_{31}+a_{32}-S/3$	$2*S/3-a_{32}$	$2*S/3-a_{31}$	$a_{33}+a_{34}-S/3$	$2*S/3-a_{34}$	$2*S/3-a_{33}$	$a_{35}+a_{36}-S/3$	$2*S/3-a_{36}$	$2*S/3-a_{35}$	$a_{37}+a_{38}-S/3$	$2*S/3-a_{38}$	$2*S/3-a_{37}$	$a_{39}+a_{40}-S/3$	$2*S/3-a_{40}$	$2*S/3-a_{39}$
$4*S/3-2*a_{31}-a_{32}$	$S/3$	$2*a_{31}+a_{32}-2*S/3$	$4*S/3-2*a_{33}-a_{34}$	$S/3$	$2*a_{33}+a_{34}-2*S/3$	$4*S/3-2*a_{35}-a_{36}$	$S/3$	$2*a_{35}+a_{36}-2*S/3$	$4*S/3-2*a_{37}-a_{38}$	$S/3$	$2*a_{37}+a_{38}-2*S/3$	$4*S/3-2*a_{39}-a_{40}$	$S/3$	$2*a_{39}+a_{40}-2*S/3$
a_{31}	a_{32}	$S-a_{31}-a_{32}$	a_{33}	a_{34}	$S-a_{33}-a_{34}$	a_{35}	a_{36}	$S-a_{35}-a_{36}$	a_{37}	a_{38}	$S-a_{37}-a_{38}$	a_{39}	a_{40}	$S-a_{39}-a_{40}$
$a_{41}+a_{42}-S/3$	$2*S/3-a_{42}$	$2*S/3-a_{41}$	$a_{43}+a_{44}-S/3$	$2*S/3-a_{44}$	$2*S/3-a_{43}$	$a_{45}+a_{46}-S/3$	$2*S/3-a_{46}$	$2*S/3-a_{45}$	$a_{47}+a_{48}-S/3$	$2*S/3-a_{48}$	$2*S/3-a_{47}$	$a_{49}+a_{50}-S/3$	$2*S/3-a_{50}$	$2*S/3-a_{49}$
$4*S/3-2*a_{41}-a_{42}$	$S/3$	$2*a_{41}+a_{42}-2*S/3$	$4*S/3-2*a_{43}-a_{44}$	$S/3$	$2*a_{43}+a_{44}-2*S/3$	$4*S/3-2*a_{45}-a_{46}$	$S/3$	$2*a_{45}+a_{46}-2*S/3$	$4*S/3-2*a_{47}-a_{48}$	$S/3$	$2*a_{47}+a_{48}-2*S/3$	$4*S/3-2*a_{49}-a_{50}$	$S/3$	$2*a_{49}+a_{50}-2*S/3$
a_{41}	a_{42}	$S-a_{41}-a_{42}$	a_{43}	a_{44}	$S-a_{43}-a_{44}$	a_{45}	a_{46}	$S-a_{45}-a_{46}$	a_{47}	a_{48}	$S-a_{47}-a_{48}$	a_{49}	a_{50}	$S-a_{49}-a_{50}$

● Details

*It is constructed in such a way that each block of order 3 is a magic square of order 3. The letter S represents the magic sum of each block of order 3. The magic sum of order 15 is $5 \times S$. We call it a **self-made** as choosing any numbers for A_1 to A_{50} and the magic sum, we always get a magic square of order 15. Sometimes we may call it as **algebraic magic square for reduced entries**. It requires only 50 entries instead of 225. See below two examples:*

Example 3.33. *Let's consider a following magic square based on the Result 1*

mgc	15x15 https://numbers-magic.com/ https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/ ©IJT														243
11	14	19	17	20	35	38	-77	41	44	59	62	-173	65	68	243
47	23	-16	26	1	71	47	8	50	-95	95	71	32	74	-191	243
-1	13	29	53	-13	23	-83	53	77	11	47	-179	77	101	35	243
35	17	2	-14	41	59	41	26	-110	65	83	65	50	-206	89	243
-11	14	47	-1	32	-107	38	71	23	56	-203	62	95	47	80	243
107	110	-359	107	116	83	86	-269	89	92	131	134	-461	137	140	243
143	119	74	122	-377	119	95	56	98	-287	167	143	104	146	-479	243
89	-365	125	155	77	71	-275	101	125	59	119	-467	149	173	107	243
137	113	92	-398	137	107	89	74	-302	113	155	137	122	-494	161	243
-395	104	149	95	128	-299	86	119	71	104	-491	134	167	119	152	243
155	158	-557	161	164	179	182	-653	185	188	203	206	-749	209	212	243
191	167	128	170	-575	215	191	152	194	-671	239	215	176	218	-767	243
143	-563	173	197	131	167	-659	197	221	155	191	-755	221	245	179	243
179	161	146	-590	185	203	185	170	-686	209	227	209	194	-782	233	243
-587	158	191	143	176	-683	182	215	167	200	-779	206	239	191	224	243
243	243	243	243	243	243	243	243	243	243	243	243	243	243	243	243

The blocks of order 3 are a magic squares of order 3 with equal magic sum $S_{3 \times 3} := 42$ resulting in magic sum of order 15 as $S_{15 \times 15} := 210$.

Example 3.34. *Let's consider a following magic square based on the Result 1*

mgc	15x15 https://numbers-magic.com/ https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/ ©IJT												255		
-10	30	31	-6	28	29	-2	26	27	2	24	25	6	22	23	255
58	17	-24	52	17	-18	46	17	-12	40	17	-6	34	17	0	255
3	4	44	5	6	40	7	8	36	9	10	32	11	12	28	255
10	20	21	14	18	19	18	16	17	22	14	15	26	12	13	255
28	17	6	22	17	12	16	17	18	10	17	24	4	17	30	255
13	14	24	15	16	20	17	18	16	19	20	12	21	22	8	255
30	10	11	34	8	9	38	6	7	42	4	5	46	2	3	255
-2	17	36	-8	17	42	-14	17	48	-20	17	54	-26	17	60	255
23	24	4	25	26	0	27	28	-4	29	30	-8	31	32	-12	255
50	0	1	54	-2	-1	58	-4	-3	62	-6	-5	66	-8	-7	255
-32	17	66	-38	17	72	-44	17	78	-50	17	84	-56	17	90	255
33	34	-16	35	36	-20	37	38	-24	39	40	-28	41	42	-32	255
70	-10	-9	74	-12	-11	78	-14	-13	82	-16	-15	86	-18	-17	255
-62	17	96	-68	17	102	-74	17	108	-80	17	114	-86	17	120	255
43	44	-36	45	46	-40	47	48	-44	49	50	-48	51	52	-52	255
255	255	255	255	255	255	255	255	255	255	255	255	255	255	255	255

The blocks of order 3 are a magic squares of order 3 with equal magic sum $S_{3 \times 3} := 51$ resulting in magic sum of order 15 as $S_{15 \times 15} := 255$.

For more studied toward this direction see the author's work [57, 58, 59, 60, 61, 62, 63, 64].

3.4.3 Double-Digit Bordered

Result 3. *Let's consider a following double-digit bordered algebraic magic square of order 15 with reduced entries:*

a48	a49	a50	a51	a52	a53	a54	a55	a56	a57	a58	a59	(13/3)*S-a59-a58-a57-a56-a55-a54-a53-a52-a51-a50-a49-a48	(2/3)*S-a60	a60
(2/3)*S-a48	(2/3)*S-a49	(2/3)*S-a50	(2/3)*S-a51	(2/3)*S-a52	(2/3)*S-a53	(2/3)*S-a54	(2/3)*S-a55	(2/3)*S-a56	(2/3)*S-a57	(2/3)*S-a58	(2/3)*S-a59	a59+a58+a57+a56+a55+a54+a53+a52+a51+a50+a49+a48-(11/3)*S	(2/3)*S-a61	a61
(13/3)*S-a92-a93-a89-a90-a91-a88-a84-a85-a86-2*a83+a60-a87-	a92+a93+a89+a90+a91+a88+a84+a85+a86+2*a83-a60+a87+a61-(11/3)*S	a17	a18	a19	a20	a21	a22	a23	a24	3*S-a17-a18-a19-a20-a21-a22-a23-a24	(2/3)*S-a25	a25	(2/3)*S-a62	a62
a93	(2/3)*S-a93	(2/3)*S-a17	(2/3)*S-a18	(2/3)*S-a19	(2/3)*S-a20	(2/3)*S-a21	(2/3)*S-a22	(2/3)*S-a23	(2/3)*S-a24	a17+a18+a19+a20+a21+a22+a23+a24-(7/3)*S	(2/3)*S-a26	a26	(2/3)*S-a63	a63
a92	(2/3)*S-a92	3*S-a47-a46-a45-a44-a43-a42-2*a41+a25-a26	a47+a46+a45+a44+a43+a42+2*a41-a25+a26-(7/3)*S	a3	a4	a5	a6	(5/3)*S-a3-a4-a5-a6	(2/3)*S-a7	a7	(2/3)*S-a27	a27	(2/3)*S-a64	a64
a91	(2/3)*S-a91	a47	(2/3)*S-a47	(2/3)*S-a3	(2/3)*S-a4	(2/3)*S-a5	(2/3)*S-a6	a3+a4+a5+a6-S	(2/3)*S-a8	a8	(2/3)*S-a28	a28	(2/3)*S-a65	a65
a90	(2/3)*S-a90	a46	(2/3)*S-a46	(5/3)*S+a7-a8-2*a14-a15-a16	a8+2*a14+a15+a16-S-a7	a1+a2-S/3	2*S/3-a2	2*S/3-a1	(2/3)*S-a9	a9	(2/3)*S-a29	a29	(2/3)*S-a66	a66
a89	(2/3)*S-a89	a45	(2/3)*S-a45	a16	(2/3)*S-a16	4*S/3-2*a1-a2	S/3	2*a1+a2-2*S/3	(2/3)*S-a10	a10	(2/3)*S-a30	a30	(2/3)*S-a67	a67
a88	(2/3)*S-a88	a44	(2/3)*S-a44	a15	(2/3)*S-a15	a1	a2	S-a1-a2	a7+a8+a9+a10-S	(5/3)*S-a7-a8-a9-a10	(2/3)*S-a31	a31	(2/3)*S-a68	a68
a87	(2/3)*S-a87	a43	(2/3)*S-a43	a14	(2/3)*S-a14	a4+2*a11+a12+a13-S-a3	(2/3)*S-a13	(2/3)*S-a12	(2/3)*S-a11	(2/3)*S+a3-a4-a11	(2/3)*S-a32	a32	(2/3)*S-a69	a69
a86	(2/3)*S-a86	a42	(2/3)*S-a42	a8+a14-a7	(2/3)*S+a7-a8-a14	(5/3)*S+a3-a4-2*a11-a12-a13	a13	a12	a11	a4+a11-a3	a25+a26+a27+a28+a29+a30+a31+a32-(7/3)*S	3*S-a25-a26-a27-a28-a29-a30-a31-a32	(2/3)*S-a70	a70
a85	(2/3)*S-a85	a41	(2/3)*S-a41	a39+a38+a37+a36+a35+a34+2*a33-a17+a18-(7/3)*S	(2/3)*S-a39	(2/3)*S-a38	(2/3)*S-a37	(2/3)*S-a36	(2/3)*S-a35	(2/3)*S-a34	(2/3)*S-a33	(2/3)*S+a17-a18-a33	(2/3)*S-a71	a71
a84	(2/3)*S-a84	a26+a41-a25	(2/3)*S+a25-a26-a41	3*S-a39-a38-a37-a36-a35-a34-2*a33+a17-a18	a39	a38	a37	a36	a35	a34	a33	a18+a33-a17	a71+a70+a69+a68+a67+a66+a65+a64+a63+a62+a61-(11/3)*S	(13/3)*S-a71-a70-a69-a68-a67-a66-a65-a64-a63-a62-a61
a83	(2/3)*S-a83	2*a72+a73+a74+a75+a76+a77+a78+a79+a80+a81+a82-a48+a49-(11/3)*S	(2/3)*S-a82	(2/3)*S-a81	(2/3)*S-a80	(2/3)*S-a79	(2/3)*S-a78	(2/3)*S-a77	(2/3)*S-a76	(2/3)*S-a75	(2/3)*S-a74	(2/3)*S-a73	(2/3)*S-a72	(2/3)*S+a48-a49-a72
a61+a83-a60	(2/3)*S+a60-a61-a83	(13/3)*S-2*a72-a73-a74-a75-a76-a77-a78-a79-a80-a81-a82+a48-a49	a82	a81	a80	a79	a78	a77	a76	a75	a74	a73	a72	a49+a72-a48

• Details

It is a composed of four equal sums magic rectangles of orders 2×8 and 2×12 (equal in each case) embedded with a magic square of order 6. This magic square of order 6 is again composed of four equal sums magic squares of order 3. Since the magic square of order 3 requires magic sum as multiple of 3, otherwise we may have decimal entries. The magic sums of orders 10 and 14 are also multiple of 3. The magic sum of orders 10 and 14 are given as $S_{10 \times 10} := \frac{10S}{3}$ and $S_{14 \times 14} := \frac{14S}{3}$, where S is the magic sum of order 3. In this case the magic sum of order 6 is given as $S_{6 \times 6} := 2S$.

Below are two examples based on the Result 3

Example 3.35. Let's consider following two examples based on the Result 3:

15	mgc	15x15 https://numbers-magic.com/ https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/ ©IJT														315	15	mgc	15x15 https://numbers-magic.com/ https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/ ©IJT														360
	49	50	51	52	53	54	55	56	57	58	59	60	-381	-19	61	315		49	50	51	52	53	54	55	56	57	58	59	60	-342	-13	61	360
	-7	-8	-9	-10	-11	-12	-13	-14	-15	-16	-17	-18	423	-20	62	315		-1	-2	-3	-4	-5	-6	-7	-8	-9	-10	-11	-12	390	-14	62	360
	-791	833	18	19	20	21	22	23	24	25	17	16	26	-21	63	315		-752	800	18	19	20	21	22	23	24	25	44	22	26	-15	63	360
	94	-52	24	23	22	21	20	19	18	17	25	15	27	-22	64	315		94	-46	30	29	28	27	26	25	24	23	4	21	27	-16	64	360
	93	-51	-169	211	4	5	6	7	83	34	8	14	28	-23	65	315		93	-45	-142	190	4	5	6	7	98	40	8	20	28	-17	65	360
	92	-50	48	-6	38	37	36	35	-41	33	9	13	29	-24	66	315		92	-44	48	0	44	43	42	41	-50	39	9	19	29	-18	66	360
	91	-49	47	-5	41	1	-16	39	40	32	10	12	30	-25	67	315		91	-43	47	1	56	-8	-19	45	46	38	10	18	30	-19	67	360
	90	-48	46	-4	17	25	77	21	-35	31	11	11	31	-26	68	315		90	-42	46	2	17	31	89	24	-41	37	11	17	31	-20	68	360
	89	-47	45	-3	16	26	2	3	58	-25	67	10	32	-27	69	315		89	-41	45	3	16	32	2	3	67	-34	82	16	32	-21	69	360
	88	-46	44	-2	15	27	-11	28	29	30	29	9	33	-28	70	315		88	-40	44	4	15	33	-20	34	35	36	35	15	33	-22	70	360
	87	-45	43	-1	16	26	53	14	13	12	13	89	-47	-29	71	315		87	-39	43	5	16	32	68	14	13	12	13	68	-20	-23	71	360
	86	-44	42	0	147	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	7	-30	72	315		86	-38	42	6	126	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	13	-24	72	360
	85	-43	43	-1	-105	40	39	38	37	36	35	34	35	567	-525	315		85	-37	43	5	-78	40	39	38	37	36	35	34	35	534	-486	360
	84	-42	701	-41	-40	-39	-38	-37	-36	-35	-34	-33	-32	-31	-32	315		84	-36	668	-35	-34	-33	-32	-31	-30	-29	-28	-27	-26	-25	-26	360
	85	-43	-659	83	82	81	80	79	78	77	76	75	74	73	74	315		85	-37	-620	83	82	81	80	79	78	77	76	75	74	73	74	360
	315	315	315	315	315	315	315	315	315	315	315	315	315	315	315	315		360	360	360	360	360	360	360	360	360	360	360	360	360	360	360	

The magic sums are:

- First example: $S_{3 \times 3} := 63$, $S_{7 \times 7} := 147$, $S_{11 \times 11} := 231$ and $S_{15 \times 15} := 315$.
- Second example: $S_{3 \times 3} := 72$, $S_{7 \times 7} := 168$, $S_{11 \times 11} := 264$ and $S_{15 \times 15} := 360$.

For more details refer Taneja [65, 66].

4 Author's Contribution to Magic Squares and Recreation of Numbers

For author's contribution to **magic squares** and **recreation of numbers** please see the links below:

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